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smashHit Methodology (final)

WP 2

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Project Summary

The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators. The Framework will provide methods and tools, such as Smart Data Dispatcher, to assure common consent over data shared using semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owners, data providers, service providers and users. These tools are specifically critical for enormous volumes on data streaming from the usage of mass products with cyber physical features (e.g. vehicles). These data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, but their combination with other personal and industrial data is subject to complex ownership and consent aspects, as the data streaming from these products belong to persons or organizations who are owners or users of the products. The project will be based on the solutions developed or under development in previous and current projects (AutoMat, Cross-CPP, CAMPANEO, DALICC etc.). smashHit is driven by two industrial Business Cases involving several existing industrial and personal data platforms owned by the leading data providers in three diverse sectors (automotive industry, insurance, smart city), and will provide three demonstrators of various applications of the developed solutions.

Project Consortium

ATB	Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH	Germany
UIBK	University of Innsbruck	Austria
LUH	Leibniz Universität Hannover	Germany
TOG	X/Open Company Limited	United Kingdom
VW	Volkswagen AG	Germany
LN	LexisNexis Risk Solutions (Europe)	Ireland
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy	Finland
INFT	Infotripla Oy	Finland
ATOS	ATOS Spain	Spain
UBO	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn	Germany

More Information

ATB Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH (Coordinator)
 Represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by: Christian Wolff
 E-Mail: wolff@atb-bremen.de
 Phone: +49 (0)421 / 22092 33

Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH, ATB
 HRB 13969 HB
 Wiener Straße 1
 28359 Bremen
 Germany
 Web: <https://www.atb-bremen.de/>

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Document Summary

This Deliverable D2.2 “Final smashHit Methodology” provides an overview of developed set of support material, which serve the different stakeholders of the smashHit value chain as basic guidelines for participating in the overall smashHit workflow.

One of the key objectives of the support material is to empower smashHit stakeholders to easily implement specified and developed procedures and tools, as well as to understand offered functions and tools. Thus, the developed support materials address organisational, administrative and contractual measures concerning the interaction of the various stakeholders with the smashHit framework solution.

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1 Introduction

In addition to the specification and implementation of the smashHit framework (smashHit platform, consent certification, automatic contracting tool, data use traceability etc.) the project has developed and provided a set of support material, which serve the different stakeholders of the smashHit value chain (data owners in their role as data subjects, data providers, data processors/controllers) as basic guidelines for participating in the overall smashHit workflow.

A key challenge of the smashHit project is to address a privacy aware consent and contract management for secure sharing of data from and between diverse platforms including agreed consent and legal rules among the stakeholders (data owners, data providers, data processors). Therefore, the Methodology provides guidelines on how to use the smashHit platform and the privacy and security preserving services to integrate and assure data owner and service users consent and compliance with legal rules of all involved stakeholders among diverse platforms. This Methodology provides the method to translate the legal rules of the stakeholders in the semantic model which is being used by the smashHit solution to achieve a platform overlapping consent certification service.

In this context, one of the key objectives of the support material is to empower smashHit platform stakeholders to easily implement specified and developed procedures and tools and to understand offered functions and tools.

The developed support materials also address organisational, administrative and contractual measures concerning the interaction of the various stakeholders with the smashHit platform.

To achieve such an envisaged Methodology Concept and to identify required tailored support material to be developed, the specific view and needs for each of the smashHit platform solution stakeholders was taken into account, which resulted into the following four types of support materials:

- **Developer Guidelines:** This type represents specific developer guidelines for industrial smashHit platform users (data providers and data processors/controllers), aiming to give these user groups all necessary knowledge on how to connect their systems with smashHit.
- **User Guidelines:** This type represents specific user guidelines for the smashHit solution to end users (data owners, data providers, data processors/controllers, smashHit platform administrator), aiming to help them on how to use the platform (e.g. the specific functionalities provided by the platform, such as user authentication, consent/contract certification, data use traceability, automatic contracting etc.) and gives knowledge about the different functionalities available.
- **Concept Papers:** This document provides easy understandable general descriptions of the key innovative project outcome, like the overall smashHit platform solution and the semantic model.
- **smashHit Platform Policy Guidelines:** As a complementary support material, this document provides legal, privacy and consent regulations for key processes/activities in respect to the actions/roles of the various stakeholders and their interaction required for the operation of the smashHit platform solution.

The developed support material is of large scale (6 documents with overall 111 pages), and is included as appendix to this document (sections 2 to 8). Given the fact that all support materials are of public nature, they will be made available on the smashHit website: <https://smashhit.eu/publications>

The following Table 1-1 gives a more detailed overview on all developed methodology support material, including a short description of each document purpose and the targeted smashHit stakeholder group.

Note: The full technical details of each module can be found in their respective full prototype (confidential) reports, see [1], [2], and [3]. These smashHit user guides are the hands-on user and developer guides for the technical deliverables.

Table 1-1: Overview of smashHit Methodology Material

	Support Material Name	Short summary of support material	Addressed Key Stakeholder groups	Annex Number
User & Developer Guide (combined)	smashHit Platform User & Developer Guide Data Provider & Data Processor	<p>This guide aims to help users and developers with a data provider and/or processor role on how to use the smashHit platform and gives knowledge about the different platform functionalities available. Main topics covered by this guide are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organization registration request - First login and additional organization users' setup - Application registration and configuration - Consent template definition - Certificate creation and management - Consent notifications - Contract management - Traceability component 	Data Provider Data Processor	Annex 1: User & Developer Guidelines Data Provider & Data Processor
User Guide	smashHit Platform User Guide Data Owner	This guide aims to help users with a data owner role on how to use the smashHit platform and gives knowledge about the different functionalities available. It provides an overview of a standard step-by-step platform usage including the steps Registration, Consent Management, User Preferences Management.	Data Owner	Annex 2: User Guidelines Data Owner
	smashHit Platform User Guide Administrator	This guide aims to help users with a platform administrator role on how to use the smashHit platform and gives knowledge about the different platform functionalities available. It covers in particular some of the administrator exclusive functionalities, such as the organisation management.	Platform Administrator/Operator	Annex 3: User Guidelines Platform Administrator
Concept Papers	smashHit Overall Concept White Paper	In this white paper, more details about the smashHit system concept as a whole are being presented, leading from today's constraints in consent/contract processes to how smashHit is facing those challenges with its novel trusted and secure system concept, highlighting the key innovations in this field.	Platform Administrator/Operator Data Owner Data Provider Data Processor	Annex 4: smashHit Overall Concept White Paper

	smashHit Semantic Model Technical Essay	This technical essay gives an overview over the developed smashHit semantic model (also known as smashHit core ontology). The design process of the model is showcased, starting with the motivation for using semantic models in smashHit and the challenges in ontology design in general. The essay concludes with how we have faced these challenges and gives some practical application examples within the project.	Platform Administrator/Operator Data Owner Data Provider Data Processor	Annex 5: smashHit Semantic Model Technical Essay
smashHit Platform Internal Policy	smashHit Platform Internal Policy Guidelines	These process/activity related Methodology Guidelines describes regulations in respect to the interaction between the key smashHit Stakeholders with the platform, such as contractual and privacy/security issues. This guide is divided into two main parts. The first part looks at contractual regulations. It is meant to guide those who engage in digital or smart contracts within the infrastructure of smashHit. The second part focuses on privacy and security issues around the processing of personal data.	Platform Administrator/Operator Data Owner Data Provider Data Processor	Annex 6: smashHit Internal Policies Guidelines

2 References

- [1] smashHit Consortium, *Deliverable D2.6 Full Prototype of Semantic Based Smart Data Dispatcher and Context Sensitivity solutions*, 2022.
- [2] smashHit Consortium, *Deliverable D3.4 Full Prototype of Data Use Traceability and Automatic Contracting*, 2022.
- [3] smashHit Consortium, *Deliverable D4.4 Full Prototype of S&P Mechanisms, and Privacy Metrics*, 2022.

3 Annex 1: User & Developer Guidelines Data Provider & Data Processor

Smart Dispatcher For Secure And Controlled Sharing Of Distributed
Personal And Industrial Data

smashHit

User & Developer Guide

Data Provider
Data Processor

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Introduction

Purpose

This guide aims to help organization users and developers with a data “provider” and/or “processor” technical role¹ on how to use the smashHit platform and gives knowledge about the different functionalities available.

Audience

This guide is meant for and solely for organization users of the smashHit platform with data “provider” or “processor” role. Other roles can find their own user guides under smashhit.eu.

Scope

The contents of this guide are meant to be taken into consideration only when using the smashHit platform and will only cover functionalities meant to be used by the roles stated above.

The smashHit team does not take responsibility for improper use of the application or the data provided when not following the instructions given in this guide.

Troubleshooting

For any questions or inquiries about the use of the smashHit platform web application or the contents of it or this guide, or if you find there is no content in this guide for some functionality, please forward it to: info@smashhit.eu

Contact

smashHit Project website: <https://smashhit.eu>

smashHit platform support: info@smashhit.eu

¹ Organizations “providing” the data or just “processing” data (in the technical sense of the term) might adopt either a data “controller” or “processor” role as stated by GDPR in different scenarios, to be defined in a case-by-case basis, depending on the terms for the processing of personal data.

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Guide

Basic knowledge

The objective of the smashHit framework is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a framework to facilitate the processing of data subject consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. While these data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, they often require the management of a complex set of consent chains.

The main goal of smashHit is thus to overcome these obstacles by offering a set of methods and tools to facilitate the management of consents, supported by semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data subjects, data controllers and data processors.

Step by step

Data provider/processor organizations in smashHit are meant to be managed through the usage of “organization user” accounts. These organization users can manage both administrative and developer-oriented tasks, ranging from the definition of consent templates through the web interface, to the integration with smashHit APIs for consent management. This guide will cover the different options and processes to follow in order for an organization to integrate their application(s) with the smashHit framework.

The following steps would represent the typical tasks to be performed by an organization user in order to make use of smashHit:

- Organization registration request
- First login and additional organization users' setup
- Application registration and configuration
- Consent template definition
- Consent creation and management
- Consent notifications
- Contract management
- Use of Traceability component.

Registration

The first step for organization users would be to fill a registration form. From the landing page², users can click the “Sign Up!” button to submit a registration request in smashHit (Figure 1) that will be reviewed and accepted (or rejected) by an administrator.

² <https://smashhit.ari-mobility.eu>

Sign up

Role	Organization
Organization Name	[Redacted]
Admin Name	[Redacted]
Admin Email	[Redacted]

[Cancel](#) [Sign up](#)

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Figure 1: Organization registration

As the administrator validates the organization registration request, an email will be sent to the address specified by the organization with instructions on how to access smashHit. Now, from the landing page, organization users can click “Sign in” and log in with their assigned credentials, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Sign in

Once signed in in smashHit, organization users will be shown a quick resume of their organization details & organization admin users, as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Organization landing page

In the left sidebar, the organization user can click “Organization”, “Application”, “Consent templates”, or “Certificates” to access the different functionalities.

Clicking “Organization”, will open the interface seen in Figure 4, where the user can see a brief list of their applications and consent templates items, as well as add or remove additional users with admin rights for the organization.

Figure 4: Organization management

Application management

As an organization, the first step to integrate an application that will interact with users’ personal data is to model the application itself in the platform through the “Application” tab.

In the context of smashHit, an application represents specific pieces of software owned by an organization, that will process personal data, and thus has the legal requirement to request for the data subject’s consent. The concept of application is an abstraction for organizations to easily aggregate a set of consents used by the same application.

Depending on the type of processing to be done by the application, the organization might take a data controller or processor role, something which will be defined later in the consent template for each case.

From the “Applications” tab (Figure 5), the organization can manage existing applications for their organization (Figure 6) or register a new one (Figure 7).

Figure 5: Applications list

Figure 6: Application management

Edit Application

ID: [REDACTED]

NAME: [REDACTED]

DATA CONTROLLER: [REDACTED]

API KEY: [REDACTED]

APPLICATION MAPPING DATA	NAME	TYPE	OPTIONAL	PRIVATE	
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	string	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

DATA TRACEABILITY:

DEFERRED USER CREATION:

CONSENT TEMPLATES	NAME	ID	PURPOSE	ACTIONS
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	<input type="checkbox"/>
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	<input type="checkbox"/>

ISSUER NOTIFICATION URL: [REDACTED]

RECIPIENT NOTIFICATION URL: [REDACTED]

TOKEN: USE JWT:

Figure 7: Application registration

As it can be seen from the figure above, in order to model an application, an organization must provide:

Field name	Description
Name	A common name to identify the application.
Application mapping data	Set of custom fields that the application developer can declare for the application.

	<p>If defined, the application can send an “applicationMappings” object in the certificate request setting these values, so that smashHit will store and distribute these fields in future notifications about the consent certificate.</p> <p>The purpose of setting these fields is to facilitate the integration and mapping smashHit objects (consent details, application or data subject ids...) with internal ids used by the organization, for example, a vehicle identification number, or product ID.</p> <p>Fields flagged as “private” will only be forwarded to the certificate issuer application but hidden from other recipients of the consent.</p>
Data traceability	Whether to enable or disable the traceability capabilities for the application ³ .
Deferred user creation	<p>If enabled, the application can set a personalData.email object in the consent “/certificate” request so that smashHit will create a new account for the dataSubject using the email provided (if it doesn’t exist already).</p> <p>If disabled, the application must manually register the data owner through a POST request to the /dataOwner endpoint available in the smashHit API⁴.</p>
Consent templates	All the consents to be requested by an organization’s application must follow one of the consent templates specified here. See the next section for details on the consent templates.
Issuer/recipient notification url	The url where smashHit will send a notification about new consents or changes to existing consent in which this application is involved. See the notification section for more details.
Token: use JWT	Whether the notification request from smashHit should include a bearer or JWT token ⁵ .

Once the application is registered, please note that smashHit will assign it an “api key” that can be consulted from the application detail view. Please take note of this value as it will be used later for certificate generation.

Consent template management

Consents in smashHit must always follow a custom, pre-defined template. Similar to applications, consent templates can be listed (Figure 8), managed (Figure 9) and defined (Figure 10, Figure 11) from the “Consent templates” tab.

³ Depending on the use case, the organization should define a specific consent template (and ask the user for consent) regarding the processing of data for traceability purposes.

⁴ <https://smashhit.ari-mobility.eu/swagger/>

⁵ Please contact smashHit staff to obtain the JWT secret for token validation

Figure 8: Consent template list

Figure 9: Consent template management

Edit Consent Template

NAME: [Redacted]

ORGANIZATION: [Redacted]

PURPOSE: Service Provision

PURPOSE DESCRIPTION: [Redacted]

PERSONAL DATA

CATEGORY	DATA																		
cardata	FIELD: [Redacted] x [Redacted] x																		
Contact	FIELD: <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Email Address</td><td>x</td> <td>Telephone Number</td><td>x</td> <td>streetNumber</td><td>x</td> </tr> <tr> <td>streetName</td><td>x</td> <td>unitNumber</td><td>x</td> <td>city</td><td>x</td> </tr> <tr> <td>state</td><td>x</td> <td>country</td><td>x</td> <td>zip</td><td>x</td> </tr> </table>	Email Address	x	Telephone Number	x	streetNumber	x	streetName	x	unitNumber	x	city	x	state	x	country	x	zip	x
Email Address	x	Telephone Number	x	streetNumber	x														
streetName	x	unitNumber	x	city	x														
state	x	country	x	zip	x														

Figure 10: Consent template definition (I)

Identifying

FIELD:

firstName	x	middleName	x	lastName	x
Birth Date	x				

SECTOR: Financial and Insurance Activities

DATA PROCESSING: Collect

AGENTS:

APPLICATION	ROLE
[Redacted]	dataProcessor

Buttons: Cancel, Confirm changes

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Figure 11: Consent template definition (II)

As it can be seen from the figures above, the following fields must be defined for each consent template. The formulary is guided/restricted by the smashHitCore Ontology⁶ (for more details see the smashHit semantic model technical essay on the smashHit website at <https://smashhit.eu/publications>), please refer to the appropriate field in the ontology for a detailed definition and list of possible values.

Field name	Description
Name	A common name to identify the consent template.
Purpose	The purpose of the processing of personal data.
Purpose description	Optional, detailed description of the purpose.
Personal data	List of types of personal data involved in the consent.
Sector	Business sector applicable to the processing.
Data processing	List of processing operations to perform with the personal data.
Agents	List referencing each of the organizations involved in the consent as well as their role in the processing of personal data. The organization is referenced through its relevant application, which will be notified of the creation/modification of consents following this template.

Similar to applications, consent templates are assigned an ID by smashHit as they are created. Please take note of this value as it will be used later for certificate creation.

Consent management

After this initial setup of the organization, application, and consent templates, organizations can start generating consent “certificates” through the smashHit.

In the context of smashHit, a consent “certificate” is a JSON object which aggregates a group of consents, requested by the same organization (through one of its applications) to a given data subject. After asking the data subject for a set of consents through its application, following the list of previously defined consent templates, the organization sends smashHit a request to “certify” the consents.

In short, this “certification” step consists of smashHit internally validating, signing, storing, and distributing the consents to Agents involved.

While the previous steps can be achieved through calls to the smashHit API directly, it is recommended to use the GUI as described. The next steps however do require the integration of some calls to the smashHit APIs.

Following industry standards, the smashHit APIs require an oauth2 token for authorization (to be included in each request as an “x-auth-token” header). In the case of smashHit, this is managed through Keyrock IdM⁷, so an access token can be generated through a standard oauth2 procedure⁸ using your organization user credentials and the client_id and client_secret provided by the smashHit team, as the example seen in Figure 12.

⁶ <https://smashhiteu.github.io/smashHitCore/>

⁷ Deployed at: <https://idm-smashhit.ari-mobility.eu>

⁸ See: <https://fiware-idm.readthedocs.io/en/7.4.0/api/>

The screenshot shows a REST client interface for a POST request to the endpoint `{{idm}}/oauth2/token`. The request body is form-urlencoded and contains the following parameters:

KEY	VALUE	DESCRIPTION
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> grant_type	password	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> username	{{user}}	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> password	{{password}}	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> client_id	{{client-id-prod}}	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> client_secret	{{client-secret-prod}}	

The response is a JSON object:

```

1  {
2    "access_token": "ac249dfc94b97e6db335ea1024d0b421b8e820c4",
3    "token_type": "Bearer",
4    "expires_in": 3599,
5    "refresh_token": "9804a82c5edb7185b305992503a5bd036f1feebe",
6    "scope": [
7      "bearer"
8    ]
9  }

```

The response status is 200 OK, with a response time of 470 ms and a size of 763 B.

Figure 12: Access token generation

Once the organization has configured its application and its consent templates, the application can start registering new data subjects (users with data owner role) and consent “certificates” in smashHit. As mentioned earlier, applications can either:

- Manage data owner registration manually from the smashHit API (`/dataOwner` endpoints), in which case they must set the “dataSubject” field in the certificate request as the dataOwner’s `idmId` field
- Enable the “deferredUserCreation” option for implicit registration in the certificate request itself, in which case the certificate request can include a “personalData” object with an “email” attribute, which the platform will use for registration.

again a new certificate request with the updated user selection to smashHit. smashHit will automatically handle any revocation/grant request to reflect the changes in the ACT and respond to the request with a new certificate reflecting the new changes.

Any processing errors will be returned in a “consentErrors” field. In case any error makes it impossible for smashHit to apply the new changes in the ACT’s knowledge graph, the consent will remain unchanged, while the error will be reported back to the application.

While certificates can also be queried using smashHit API (check the specification to find different methods of querying/filtering by dataOwner, application, etc.), the smashHit GUI does provide an organization interface to check the active certificate for each user, in the “Certificates” tab (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Certificates list

Organization users can also click one of the certificates to check the full details, including the status of each of the consents in the certificate (Figure 15), as well as the traceability records for a consent, assuming it is enabled for the application (Figure 16).

Figure 15: Certificate details

Figure 16: Consent traceability records

Notification endpoint

The previous section covers certificate management from point of view of the issuer application, i.e., the application which originally collects the consent from the user and handles the certificate.

However, as it has been mentioned earlier, the rest of the agents of a given consent must be notified of events affecting new and existing consents in smashHit as long as they are involved in the processing.

Even for issuer applications, it is necessary to implement some kind of notification channel as well, so that when a data subject uses the smashHit GUI to modify their consents, their application can be informed and enforce the new preferences.

As described in the Application management section earlier, organizations can configure a notification URL for their applications, so that smashHit can automatically inform them of any changes to an existing consent (or the creation of a new one, in the case of third parties).

This notification URL must follow the swagger specification defined here:

<https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/icarrilloari1/smashNotification/0.0.4>

As it can be seen from the specification, the process is simple: smashHit will send a POST request to the URL configured with the new certificate as the body (including a reference to the previous certificate, as well as the latest applicationMappings). As the notification is received by an application, the new consent selection must be enforced.

Data use traceability

This section is to help organization developers to use the Data Use traceability (DUT) component. The DUT component has two independent parts which are: Data Traceability and Re-identification. Concerning Data Traceability, the actions that could be done are: register data, initiate a data transfer, confirm an occurred transfer, get the data trace using consent or contract identifier. Concerning the re-identification part, the implemented actions aim to verify the authenticity of a leaked data (verify if a given data was modified or not) in two scenarios: First, the data subject or provider does not modify the original data, and that data is leaked and modified by an attacker. Second, the data subject modifies the original data by inserting watermark and by creating a watermarked data; this watermarked data is leaked and modified by an attacker. The actions are: re-identify fingerprint, watermark trip and find watermarked correlation.

Before going into further details, we are first going to explain how the DUT component is set up and made ready to use. As prerequisites, Python 3 has to be installed. There are two possibilities to set up DUT component which are traceability package and docker.

- Traceability package: download the code here⁹, extract the folder, install the required dependencies (present in requirements.txt) in your working environment, then follow the step 4 mentioned in this file¹⁰.

⁹ https://github.com/uttam1216/DataUseTraceability_LUH_UBO

¹⁰ https://github.com/uttam1216/DataUseTraceability_LUH_UBO/blob/main/README.md

- Docker: install docker¹¹ (if not yet present), download the code here¹², extract the folder and follow step 5 mentioned in this file¹³.

After these previous setting steps, concluded by the onboard of your company (running the “main.py” file), you exist as an entity inside the DUT component. By opening the link <http://localhost:5001/swagger-ui/> on the server where DUT is being installed, you have access to all the functionalities offered by the Data Use Traceability Component. For each of those functionalities, here is a short description.

1. **Hashing**: get the hash of any data. It changes with a small change in the data. The input parameter is
 - a. **Trip_data***: a JSON file with trajectory coordinates of the trip.

The output will contain:

- b. **Hash**: hash of the data to be used for register data and other APIs.

2. **Fingerprinting**: fingerprints the initial raw data. The fingerprint of the data does not change with a small change in the data. The input parameter is:
 - a. **Trip_data***: a JSON file with trajectory coordinates of the trip.

The output will contain:

- b. **fingerprint**: fingerprint of the data to be used for register data and other APIs.

3. **Register Data**: register data (information about data that needs to be sent to another partner later) into the centralised manager to have a trace. During registration, following inputs are used:

- a. **access_token***: security token allowing the company to use the service.
- b. **consent_id***: identifier of the consent given by the data subject, to save and exchange the data.
- c. **contract_id**: identifier of the contract against the consent that is given by the data subject, to save and exchange the data.
- d. **creation_time**: time at which the company receiving the information from the subject, collected that data.
- e. **expiration_time**: time up to which all the companies in possession of that data are allowed to use it, as defined by contract with the data subject.
- f. **hash***: hash of the pure information without any metadata.
- g. **fingerprint**: fingerprint of the pure information without any metadata.
- h. **watermark**: fingerprint of the pure information without any metadata.

¹¹ <https://docs.docker.com/get-docker/>

¹² https://github.com/uttam1216/DataUseTraceability_LUH_UBO/tree/main/company_module_docker

¹³

https://github.com/uttam1216/DataUseTraceability_LUH_UBO/blob/main/company_module_docker/README.md

- i. **origin**: id of the data subject.

The output of this API will contain:

- j. **uri**: internal smashHit identifier of the registered data that will be used as input of other APIs like Notify Data Transfer and Confirm Data Transfer.
- k. **error**: In case of any error, the message appears as a response.

4. **Notify Data Transfer**: notify the manager about an upcoming data transfer from one company to another. To trigger the function, the sending company needs:

- a. **access_token***: security token allowing the company to use the service.
- b. **uri***: uniform resource identifier of the data, created by the manager during the registration process.
- c. **receiver_name***: smashHit registered name of the company or organisation which will receive the data

The output of this API will contain:

- d. **sender_id**: smashHit registered id of the sender to be given as input of Confirm Data Transfer API
- e. **signature_of_sender**: unique signature of the sender to be given as input of Confirm Data Transfer API
- f. **message**: success or failure message

Note: To receive the parameters and the actual data, the receiver can create a web service (collection of APIs) where endpoints for getting parameters and data could be place. Then he might send the URL to the sender. In this case the sender will have to call those 2 endpoints just after "Data transfer".

5. **Confirm Data Transfer**: acknowledge receiving of data. The parameters of this function are:

- a. **access_token***: security token allowing the company to use the service.
- b. **hash***: hash of the data or metadata, created upon the data registration phase.
- c. **sender_id***: public identifier of the company sending the data.
- d. **signature_of_sender***: signature of hash made by the sender module.
- e. **uri***: uniform resource identifier of the data created by the manager during the registration phase.

The output of this API will contain:

- f. **message**: success or failure acknowledgement message

6. **Consent Trace**: obtain log of data transfers for a given **consent_id**.

The output of this API will contain:

- a. Data Trace w.r.t. consent in JSON format **OR** a message if no trace exists.

7. **Contract Trace**: obtain log of data transfers for a given **contract_id**.

The output of this API will contain:

- a. Data Trace w.r.t. contract in JSON format **OR** a message if no trace exists.

8. **Re-Identify Fingerprint:** verify authenticity of data for the scenario in which the data owner or provider does not insert a watermark beforehand. The input is
 - a. A JSON formatted body with key names “own_data” and “trajectory”, where trajectory is the possibly leaked and modified trajectory and own_data is the data set with which the data owner wants to compare given trajectory.

Internally the Model creates a “fingerprint” or, more specifically, a vector representation of the trajectories given. This fingerprint is modification invariant, thus small modifications of the trajectory will not change the fingerprint. Further the model compares the fingerprints of the trajectory and own data set and finally predicts whether the trajectory is a modified version of a trajectory in own data.

Output:

- b. **prediction*:** True if the trajectory is a modified Version of a trajectory in own_data, false otherwise

9. **Watermark Trip:** insert watermark to create a watermarked Trip. The input to watermarking should be a trip data (JSON as in the sample file provided).

Output & Intermediate Files:

- a. Output is a watermarked trip in json format in the same as the input format. The difference between original trip and watermarked trip is that the original latitude-longitude pairs have been replaced by watermarked latitude-longitude pairs.

Input files, intermediate files and output files are saved with the corresponding names as a backup inside the company module (wtrace_data folder).

10. **Watermarked Correlation:** compute correlation to verify authenticity of data for the scenario in which the data owner or provider modifies the original data. The input to this API should be a
 - a. **watermarked_trip*:** a JSON file with trajectory coordinates of the trip for which we want to assess the authenticity.
 - b. **trip_id*:** id of the original trip data that was leaked.

The outputs are:

- c. **correlation:** a number between 0 and 1. It represents the correlation between the original watermark and the watermark that is extracted from the watermarked data (with/without intruder’s attack).
- d. **message:** the categorical description what the correlation value means

(*): Mandatory input parameters

In addition to what has been mentioned above in this section, there are some standalone modules developed, using data generation mechanisms, geolocation embeddings, concept learning approaches and semantic enrichment of spatiotemporal data, to connect data traceability and re-identification, and perform post processing analysis. Some of those components are already available in the GitHub repository¹⁴ and others are in the initial stage of development. For available components, all details about installation and setup are contained inside the README.md file of the component.

Automatic contracting

This developer guide helps the organization developers to make use of the contract module. The ACT contracts module supports the management of contracts and compliance verification checks on contracts via REST APIs and a contract UI. For better API documentation, we use the Swagger¹⁵. We can access the contract APIs endpoints from here:

<https://actool.contract.sti2.at/swagger-ui>.

The contract API endpoints divide into the following eight parts:

- (i) Contracts.
- (ii) Company.
- (iii) Contractors.
- (iv) Users.
- (v) Term Types.
- (vi) Contract Terms.
- (vii) Contractor Signatures.
- (viii) Contract Obligations (clauses).

Each part has CRUD functionality for the management of contracts. As an example, we can create a term type via the following endpoint:

<https://actool.contract.sti2.at/contract/term/type/create/>

To update a term type, the endpoint below can be used:

<https://actool.contract.sti2.at/contract/term/type/update/>

And to access all the term types we can use the endpoint:

<https://actool.contract.sti2.at/contract/term/types/>

All the endpoints have similar functionality. For a better understanding of the use of contract APIs, we provide the general steps for creating a contract:

1. Create all the term types, which require for contracts.
2. Add contractual parties.
3. Create a contract B2B/B2C with basic information (e.g., type of contract, start and ending date, etc.).

¹⁴ <https://github.com/D-Stiv/smashHitUBO.git>

¹⁵ <https://swagger.io/solutions/api-documentation/>

4. Add signatures to the contractor signatures with contract id, which is created in step 3.
5. Create contract terms with contract id, which is created in step 3.
6. Create contract obligations with (contract id, contractor id, term id), which are created in step 3, 2, 5.
7. Update the contract with contractors, contract terms, contract obligations, contract signatures.

The contract UI is another way to interact with ACT contract module. The UI can be accessed from here: <https://stiinnsbruck.github.io/smashHit-UI/build/web/index.html#/contract/>.

Guidelines for testing via UI:

1. Login form requires a contractor id, which can be generated during the registration process and can be viewed from the contract rest endpoint (<https://actool.contract.sti2.at/swagger-ui/>).

The image shows the smashHit landing page for the contract UI. It features the 'smashHit' logo at the top, a circular profile icon placeholder, and a registration form with the following fields: Name, Surname, Email, Phone Number, a dropdown for 'Select Country', a dropdown for 'Select State', a dropdown for 'Select City', and a 'Street Address' field. At the bottom of the form are two buttons: 'Register' and 'Sign In'.

Figure 17: Contract UI landing page

2. You can use the menu icon to perform different functionalities, such as creating new contract term types, creating a new contract, viewing the contractor profile, dashboard, etc.

Figure 18: Contract UI menu

3. With this GUI you can create different categories of contracts, such as a business-to-consumer contract, a business-to-business contract

Figure 19: Contract creation

The BC developer can also get the source code from the link below and run locally:

<https://github.com/AmarTauqeer/Contract>

The steps need to be performed:

1. git clone <https://github.com/AmarTauqeer/Contract.git>
2. go to the backend folder
3. update the .env file
4. sudo docker-compose -f docker-compose.yml up

Finally, the following list comprises the tools and technologies required for the contracting module to run locally:

1. [Flask](#)
2. [Flask-RESTful](#)
3. [uwsgi](#)
4. [flask apispec](#)
5. [SPARQLWrapper](#)
6. [unittest](#)
7. [Docker](#)

Context-Sensitive Security and Privacy

This guide to the context-sensitive security & privacy policies and mechanisms is for developers of other smashHit framework components as well for data provider/processor organization user developers. The S&P mechanisms consists of three main components: Policy Tool, Policy Server and Event Processing Point. These components provide support for the creation, testing, and deployment of S&P policies in the smashHit platform via REST APIs and an interactive command-driven interface. The APIs are documented using Swagger specifications which are published at:

<https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/tog-rtd/ngac-apis/1.1.1>.

The defined endpoints comprise the following categories¹⁶:

- (i) Policy administration – allows the building and manipulation of policies stored in the Policy Server.
- (ii) Policy query – allows a query to be posed to the policy decision procedures relative to a policy currently stored in the Policy Server, typically resulting in a “grant” or “deny” response.
- (iii) Event-response policy – used to report events and to configure, using the Event-Response Language (ERL), responses consisting of a sequence of commands to be performed when an associated event pattern is recognized.
- (iv) Security auditing – used to configure the audit system, including the selection of a set of audit events to be recorded in the audit log if and when they occur, and management of the audit log files.

¹⁶ There are several additional categories of API endpoints defined in the referenced Swagger specification that are TOG-RTD APIs and not used in smashHit Automatic Contracting tool.

- (v) DPLP meta-element administration – permit meta-elements defined in the Declarative Policy Language (DPL) extended for privacy (DPLP) to be added to or deleted from a policy stored in the Policy Server. These meta-elements create a GDPR-compliant abstraction layer on top of the primitive DPL policy elements.

Categories (i) policy administration, (ii) policy query and (v) DPLP meta-element administration are used by the smashHit automatic contracting tool, and may be used by other smashHit components or other BC applications in future developments. Category (iv) security auditing, is used by the Policy Server internally, and the external API is provided for use by smashHit data use traceability. The value of (iv) to smashHit generally can be enhanced as other components define security-relevant events that they can recognize and subsequently participate in the reporting of occurrences of these events through the security auditing API.

The Policy Tool provides an interactive environment in which to develop and test DPL, DPLP and ERL policies. The Tool does not provide policy file editing capabilities although it does provide the capability of incrementally building a policy by adding policy elements. The typical workflow for the Policy Tool is in conjunction with a text editor in another window. When the policy is changed in the editor and saved¹⁷, the policy file can be reloaded into the Tool for continued testing. Many of the operations available through the Server's APIs are also available as commands in the Tool. The commands and APIs are elaborated in the smashHit deliverables: D4.2 Final Specification of S&P Policies and Mechanisms, and Privacy Metrics, Section 5; and, D4.4 Full Prototype of S&P Mechanisms and Privacy Metrics, Section 5.

To test policies or applications that use NGAC through the REST APIs it is easy to build and run a local instance of the Policy Server and Event Processing Point (EPP).¹⁸ In this way testing can be done without interference with the production instance of the server. smashHit and organization developers can obtain the source for the S&P mechanisms at:

<https://github.com/tog-rtd/SmashHit.git>.

The source repository consists of a directory tree including source files and example files. Building and running the S&P mechanisms requires an installation of SWI Prolog (preferably a current or recent version) which is available for several operating environments, including Mac, Windows and Linux from:

<https://www.swi-prolog.org>.

The executables for the Policy Tool and the Policy Server are built by executing the simple script 'mkngac' in the BUILD directory (e.g. "BUILD/mkngac"), which will create the 'ngac' and 'ngac-server' executables in the BUILD directory. These are built to include the Prolog runtime environment and can be executed like ordinary executables.

After running the mkngac script the Policy Tool can be started at the OS command level by executing "BUILD/ngac". The Policy Tool has some built-in self-tests. These can be run to ensure that the Policy Tool is working correctly. The commands of the Policy Tool are in the syntax of a function call, with the command name, an optional list of parameters enclosed in parentheses, and a terminating period. The command "self_test." will run the built-in self-tests. "help." will list the available commands. "help(command)." will give more detailed help on the named command. Command

¹⁷ Some text editors, e.g. Visual Studio Code, can continuously auto save.

¹⁸ By default, the EPP is started and runs in the same process as the Policy Server. Command line options for the ngac-server are listed in D4.2, Section 5.5.1.

sequences may be packaged as predefined procedures (“procs”) by editing the procs.pl file and executed with the “proc” command, but they can more conveniently be created as command scripts in separate files and executed with the “script” command.

The Policy Server can be started at the OS command level by executing “BUILD/ngac-server”.¹⁹ The Policy Server has some command line options that are useful when starting it in a production environment. For example, the setting of the admin token for this run of the Server. The admin token is needed for all calls to the policy administration APIs. The smashHit startup procedure should distribute to components that use the APIs the chosen value for the token given to the current instance of the Server. For convenience the default token value “admin_token” can be used on local instances of the Server that are used for testing API-based interactions.

Tests that demonstrate the use of the Server’s APIs are contained in the source repository under the TEST/nn-tests directory, where may be found a number of shell command scripts that use the curl utility to invoke the APIs. These scripts send a sequence of requests to the server to test for known correct answers. These scripts run illustrative tests, they do not run exhaustive tests. A top-level script, run-nn-tests.sh, runs all of the numbered test scripts. Expected results are contained in corresponding numbered files. The script takes a single optional argument “-json” which causes the results of the run to be compared against the numbered files with “-json” suffix. The ngac-server must be running in the appropriate mode (--jsonresp the default) to get JSON responses. (See server command line options.)

An alternative method of gaining familiarity with the APIs is by using SwaggerHub to invoke the APIs²⁰ which are defined in a Swagger specification at the link given above.

Global parameters are defined in the param.pl file. Settable parameters (those that can be changed from the Policy Tool command line with the set command) are itemized in the list settable_params. For example, the parameter audit_logging is a settable parameter.

In production use smashHit components, such as the ACT, that use the Policy Server will need to build the policies in the Server using the Server’s APIs. It is the responsibility of the using application to assure that the version of a policy in the Server is current. In the event that the Server is shut down the using application will have to reestablish the policy in the appropriate state. The Server offers an API (“paapi/readpol”) to read out the current state of a policy and an API (“paapi/reset”) to reset a policy to its state when it was initially created. These APIs may be useful in managing the current state of policies in the Server. The developer of the using application(s) will need to work out a strategy for policy administration and coordinate with the platform administrator to have appropriate procedures for startup and shutdown of smashHit to implement this strategy. (See also: Platform Administrator User Guide.)

¹⁹ It is possible to start the Server from within the Policy Tool for testing but the command line options are not available when starting it this way.

²⁰ The APIs can be invoked on a locally running instance of the Server or on an instance running at ATB by editing the “host” lines near the beginning of the Swagger specification.

F.A.Q.

smashHit platform

Q: What is the smashHit platform?

A: smashHit is a platform that provides a generic, transparent way to view and manage consent certificates supported by disrupting technologies such as traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owners, data provider, and service providers.

Q: How can my organization keep track of new consents or modifications to existing ones?

A: Regardless of if you are the issuer of the consent or just an agent involved in the processing, whenever a consent status is registered in smashHit, or if the data subject changes their decision (grant/revoke), smashHit will automatically send a notification to your application via the URL provided in the configuration. Please check the “Notification endpoint” section for more details on the format.

Q: Do consent notifications requests from smashHit include any security measures?

A: Outbound notification requests from smashHit will include an ouath2 token issued by the smashHit IdM. In the same way that smashHit requires inbound requests to provide a valid authorization token, your application should expect and validate this token in the x-auth-token of any incoming request.

Q: How should I notify smashHit in case the data subject asks to revoke a given consent?

A: Any modifications to an existing consent can be processed simply by sending a new consent certificate request with the current status as selected by the data subject. The new consent certificate will replace the previous one.

Q: In the consent certificate request, how can I specify whether a consent is accepted or not by the data subject?

A: Only the id for currently accepted consent templates must be included in the certificate request (in the “consents” array), regardless of if these have changed from previous requests.

Since smashHit is already aware of which consent templates are linked to a given application, there is no need to specify consents not accepted by the data subject.

Also, since smashHit is already aware of the previous certificate, there is no need to specify changes in the request. smashHit will automatically compare the current data subject selection with the previous certificate’s and handle any necessary consent grant or revocation.

In case a specific consent has not changed its status from a request to the next one, its id and decision token will maintain their values.

Q: How can I register my users with smashHit?

A: Applications can either:

- Manage data owner registration manually from the smashHit API (/dataOwner endpoints), in which case they must set the “dataSubject” field in the certificate request as the dataOwner’s idmId field
- Enable the “deferredUserCreation” option for implicit registration in the certificate request itself, in which case the certificate request can include a “personalData” object with an “email” attribute, which the platform will use for registration.

Glossary

ACT: Automatic Contracting Tool

Agent: Entity that bears some form of responsibility in the context of a consent

Administrator: smashHit platform system administrator

Consent: As per Article 4(11) of the GDPR, 'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her

Consent template: A template defining the details of a data processing by an Agent (smashHit organization user), such as the purpose of the processing or the personal data to be processed

CSS: Context sensitivity solution

Data owner: smashHit user role which acts as the data subject according to GDPR

DPL: Declarative Policy Language

DUT: Data Use Traceability

ERL: Event response language

GDPR: Abbreviation for 'General Data Protection Regulation', a legal norm on EU level adopted in 2016, which is directly applicable within its scope and lays down rules for the processing of personal data so as to protect natural persons' fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data

Personal data: Any information which are related to an identified or identifiable natural person (Art. 4 (1) GDPR), e.g. a name or a home address

Purpose: The purpose of Data Handling/Processing

S&P: Security and privacy module

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➤ **Our vision** - Solving Consumer Consent & Data Security for Connected Car and Smart City

➤ **Further information**

This document is part of the smashHit Methodology. The complete set of documents, including other user/developer guides as well as white papers created within this scope can be found on our website:

<https://smashhit.eu/publications>

➤ **Our consortium**

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4 Annex 2: User Guidelines Data Owner

Smart Dispatcher For Secure And Controlled Sharing Of Distributed Personal And Industrial Data

User Guide

Data Owner

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 871477

Introduction

Purpose

This guide aims to help users with a data “owner” role, i.e., users who consent to the processing of their personal data and acting as data subjects according to GDPR, on how to use the smashHit platform and gives knowledge about the different functionalities available.

Audience

This guide is meant for and solely for users of the smashHit platform with data owner role. Other roles can find their own user guides under smashhit.eu.

Scope

The contents of this guide are meant to be taken into consideration only when using the smashHit platform and will only cover functionalities meant to be used by the role stated above.

The smashHit team does not take responsibility for improper use of the application or the data provided when not following the instructions given in this guide.

Troubleshooting

For any questions or inquiries about the use of the smashHit platform web application or the contents of it or this guide, or if you find there is no content in this guide for some functionality, please forward it to: info@smashhit.eu

Contact

smashHit Project website: <https://smashhit.eu>

smashHit platform support: info@smashhit.eu

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Guide

Basic knowledge

The objective of the smashHit framework is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a framework to facilitate the processing of data subject consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. While these data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, they often require the management of a complex set of consent chains.

The main goal of smashHit is thus to overcome these obstacles by offering a set of methods and tools to facilitate the management of consents, supported by semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data subjects, data controllers and data processors.

Step by step

The main goal of smashHit for data owners is to provide a generic, transparent way to view and manage consent certificates and preferences. A standard step-by-step platform usage would look like this:

- 1- Data owner account creation: As the data owner grants their first consent to any organization that uses the smashHit framework for consent management, their data owner account will be automatically created by smashHit. To facilitate things, the organization is already collecting the necessary details for their account, so there is no need for the data owner to register manually in smashHit. Once the account is set up, the data owner will receive a welcome email with details on how to access smashHit.
- 2- Consent management: in the same way the registration is handled from an organization's application directly (and managed with the smashhit framework in the background), applications will present the data owner with a consent form (based on the consent templates previously defined for the application). Once the consent is created and communicated to smashHit, the data owner can log in to their profile to check the consent details and modify the selected options, which will be informed back to the applications involved.
- 3- Context and security preferences: data owners can also set their context and security preferences so that this will allow them to have a validity control of their consents by dates and hours or for vacation dates validity. In turn, they can also have the purpose and sectors at their whim in case these decide to be changed at some point in the contract.
- 4- Finally, users can of course manage their account through their profile settings in order to change their password or generally manage their account.

Consent management

Contrary to organizations, data owners are not expected to register on their own in smashHit, their registration is instead triggered (and handled) from the organization's applications using smashHit framework APIs. Figure 1 below summarizes how smashHit handles the registration of data owner users and their consent:

Figure 1: smashHit initial registration & consent management

1. Organization A, which uses smashHit for consent management, asks one of its users (data subject) for their consent
2. Organization A confirms the reception of the consent form to the data subject, and asks smashHit to process the consent request accordingly
3. smashHit automatically creates an account for the data subject using the email provided in step 1. The consent is validated, signed and stored in smashHit
4. The data subject receives a welcome email from smashHit, confirming their registration and providing instructions on how to access the smashHit UI at <https://smashhit.ari-mobility.eu> (Figure 2) to manage their consents.
5. The consent is notified to any organizations involved in the data processing, for example:
 - a. Organization B might be a car company that needs to receive the consent to start providing data to Organization A
 - b. Organization C could be tasked with performing a specific data processing on behalf of organization A

Figure 2: smashHit landing page

So, from the landing page, the data owner user would use their assigned credentials to sign in. smashHit manages its user accounts internally using the well-known FIWARE IdM (Identity Manager) Keyrock¹. This enables smashHit to provide a robust single sign-on system that organizations can integrate in their applications too.

The first time accessing the web interface, the IdM will present a confirmation message (Figure 3) to authorize smashHit GUI to read its public profile information (the email address and the assigned role “data owner”), so that we can smashHit can properly present the interface and information according to your account and role.

Figure 3: First sign in confirmation

Once in the platform, data owners can check the active consent certificate for each application they have interacted with in the context of smashHit, as seen in Figure 4.

¹ <https://fiware-idm.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 4: Data owner certificate list

From here, data owners can check consent certificate details as well as modify their current granted consents (Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 7) for which the platform will issue the necessary revoke/grant requests internally and notify the agents affected so they can take the necessary actions to enforce the new user decisions.

Figure 5: Consent modification (I)

Figure 6: Consent modification (II)

Figure 7: Consent modification (III)

Account management

By clicking its email address at the top-right corner (Figure 8), the user can access common profile and account settings configuration pages.

Figure 8: User profile & settings menu

From the "Profile" option, the user can check its account details (Figure 9) and manage them from the Identity Manager (Figure 10).

Figure 9: User profile

Figure 10: Account management through the IdM

The “Settings” option (Figure 11) allows the user to further configure their profile and review the privacy policy². It is from here that data owners can configure their context and security preferences, as presented in the next section.

Figure 11: User settings

² For privacy policy information, please refer to smashHit’s “Policy Guidelines”

Context and security preferences

From the Data configuration Context, the data owner will be presented with some options as seen in Figure 12. Here, the user can select their desired context preferences associated with the consents, such as purposes and sector.

After the new options are processed and stored by the smashHit system, any existing consents for the user will pass a compliance check to detect any conflicts with the new preferences. Any conflicts detected by the CSS will be reported via email to the data owner, so that they can manually review each of the offending consents and choose if they want to issue a revoke request.

Figure 12: Context configuration options

The security options can be accessed from the same interface. In this case, the data owner will be presented with a similar form (Figure 13), where they can configure some policies mainly related to the date and time for which the consent is valid.

For example, a data owner might agree to share their car data only during business hours, for which they could set the holiday season and daily schedule so that it might be enforced.

Figure 13: Context security configuration options

F.A.Q.

smashHit platform

Q: What is the smashHit platform?

A: smashHit is a platform that provides a generic, transparent way to view and manage consent supported by disrupting technologies such as traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owner, data provider, and service providers.

Q: How can I join smashHit?

A: In order to make sure the process is as straight-forward as possible for data owners, your registration in smashHit will be automatically handled by us when you sign your first consent with any of the approved smashHit partners.

Instructions to access smashHit will be sent to the email address you've indicated to the organization requesting consent.

Q: What personal data does smashHit require?

A: smashHit will only use the email address provided by the organization to automatically manage your account. Even if a consent exists for sharing further personal data with any smashHit partner, such data won't ever be accessible to smashHit.

smashHit is an integral solution for consent management, but the personal data sharing flows between organizations is out of the scope of smashHit itself. Your personal data will always flow directly from the data "provider" (for example a car manufacturer) to the data "processor" (such as an insurance company).

smashHit is therefore not supposed to act as a man-in-the-middle in this data flow, but assist in managing and notifying the different actors about the consent: which personal data is to be processed and, the purpose of the processing, type of processing, and the role according to the GDPR (data controller/processor) of the different organizations involved.

Glossary

ACT: Automatic Contracting Tool

Agent: Entity that bears some form of responsibility in the context of a consent

Administrator: smashHit platform system administrator

Consent: As per Article 4(11) of the GDPR, 'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her

Consent template: A template defining the details of a data processing by an Agent (smashHit organization user), such as the purpose of the processing or the personal data to be processed

CSS: Context sensitivity solution

Data owner: smashHit user role which acts as the data subject according to GDPR

Data subject: Legal term in the GDPR used in a context where personal data is processed determining the person to whom an information is or can be related. The data subject is a natural person who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by a factor specific to her or his physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.

DUT: Data Use Traceability

GDPR: Abbreviation for 'General Data Protection Regulation', a legal norm on EU level adopted in 2016, which is directly applicable within its scope and lays down rules for the processing of personal data so as to protect natural persons' fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data

IdM: Identity Manager

Personal data: Any information which are related to an identified or identifiable natural person (Art. 4 (1) GDPR), e.g. a name or a home address

Purpose: The purpose of Data Handling/Processing

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➤ **Further information**

This document is part of the smashHit Methodology. The complete set of documents, including other user/developer guides as well as white papers created within this scope can be found on our website:

<https://smashhit.eu/publications>

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Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

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5 Annex 3: User Guidelines Platform Administrator

Smart Dispatcher For Secure And Controlled Sharing Of Distributed
Personal And Industrial Data

User Guide

Platform Administrator

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 871477

Introduction

Purpose

This guide aims to help users with a platform administrator role on how to use the smashHit platform and gives knowledge about the different functionalities available.

Audience

This guide is meant for and solely for users of the smashHit platform with platform administrator role. Other roles can find their own user guides under smashhit.eu.

Scope

The contents of this guide are meant to be taken into consideration only when using the smashHit platform and will only cover functionalities meant to be used by the role stated above.

The smashHit team does not take responsibility for improper use of the application or the data provided when not following the instructions given in this guide.

Troubleshooting

For any questions or inquiries about the use of the smashHit platform web application or the contents of it or this guide, or if you find there is no content in this guide for some functionality, please forward it to: info@smashhit.eu

Contact

smashHit Project website: <https://smashhit.eu>

smashHit platform support: info@smashhit.eu

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Guide

Basic knowledge

The objective of the smashHit framework is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a framework to facilitate the processing of data subject consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. While these data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, they often require the management of a complex set of consent chains.

The main goal of smashHit is thus to overcome these obstacles by offering a set of methods and tools to facilitate the management of consents, supported by semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data subjects, data controllers and data processors.

Step by step

The “platform administrator” role is meant for users with elevated privileges to manage most of the resources in the system, there is actually one specific functionality reserved for them, which is the management of organization registration requests. This special role is reserved for smashHit staff, and typically it will be assigned to the administrator user for the smashHit Identity Manager (IdM) itself.

As such, this kind of users are not meant to be created or managed by smashHit at all, but rather manually managed by the entity responsible for hosting the smashHit system. Thus, outside of using its privileges to provide support to other users, the main specific administrator responsibility is to review new organization registration requests and either accept them into the platform or reject them.

This guide will first offer the administrator a brief guide through the functionalities available of the UI:

- Organization registration (exclusive to the administrator)
- Application management
- Consent template management
- Data owner management

Then, the last 2 sections will offer an insight in some key points concerning the deployment of smashHit and the context-sensitive S&P module specifically, that the platform administrator should be aware of.

Organization Registration

As it can be seen in Figure 1, from the admin panel one can access the organization management interface, where the existing organizations will be listed, but most importantly, administrators can review organization registration requests by clicking the “Organization requests”. The organization registration requests list will be displayed, where the admin can either validate or reject the registration (Figure 2 Organization registration requests).

Figure 1 Administrator’s Organizations view

Figure 2 Organization registration requests

Once an organization request is accepted, the system will automatically register an account for the organization admin user, and then notify him by email with the news that the organization has been approved and next steps to access smashHit.

Application management

As explained, administrators have access to most resources in the platform, which is very helpful to provide support. From the “Application” tab, the administrator can review and manage the existing applications, as it can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Application management

Clicking the “eye” icon next to the application name will allow the admin to access the detailed view of the application and even edit its configuration in case it is necessary (Figure 4). This might be helpful in case some application must be migrated across organizations or simply to provide general support to organizations.

Figure 4 Application support

Consent template management

Similar to applications, an admin user can list and review any consent template defined in the platform by clicking the “Consent templates” option in the GUI, as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Consent template management

Data Owner management

Finally, registered data owners can be listed from the administrator panel (Figure 6), with the additional (recommended) option to access the Keyrock IdM¹ itself directly to manage advanced user settings, such as manually review and adjust roles or even reset a user password to provide support, as seen in Figure 7 and Figure 8. For more details on Keyrock administration, please refer to the official FIWARE documentation².

Figure 6 Data Owner management (I)

¹ <https://idm-smashhit.ari-mobility.eu>

² <https://fiware-idm.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 7 Data Owner management (II) IdM

Figure 8 Data Owner management (III) IdM

smashHit deployment administration

This section aims to present the key aspects of the main smashHit consent manager components. Following modern industry standards, the different components of smashHit are distributed as docker images, and all the parametrizations can be done through environment variables.

While the deployment can be of course adapted to different orchestration frameworks, the consent manager platform is currently deployed in a Rancher³-managed Kubernetes cluster, and a set of scripts and “.yaml” files are included with the source code so the deployment can be easily migrated or updated.

The following is a short description of the current deployment of smashHit, including the configuration, workloads & services, load balancing, and of course volumes to persist the data.

Configuration

This section aims to describe the deployment strategy and files utilized for the smashHit platform in a Kubernetes cluster. The deployment files’ structure can be seen in the Figure 9:

Figure 9: Deployment files structure

- The kubernetes folder holds the deployment, service and volume claim yaml files
- The deployment folder holds the config and secret folders, with the definition of the configMaps (configurable parameters such as URLs) and secrets (passwords, client credentials, certificates...)
- Finally, also in the deployment folder, a few scripts to automatize the deployment are provided:
 - Some general scripts such as envvars.sh, install.sh and login.sh allow you to first setup the necessary parameters, such as the registry credentials, rancher URL or token, then install the rancher-cli, and finally perform a login with the cluster
 - Then, for a full deployment, one can just run the fullDeploy.sh script, which automatically deploys all the components in order, configs, volumes, deployments, ingress...
 - Alternatively, the individual “deploy*.sh” scripts are provided to deploy a single specific component

³ <https://www.rancher.com/>

Workloads

A workload is an application running on Kubernetes, inside a set of pods. In Kubernetes, a Pod represents a set of running containers on the cluster. Workloads allow rules to be defined for application scheduling, scaling, and upgrading. The figure below shows the deployed workloads for smashHit, the status and the scale.

State	Name	Image	Scale
Namespace: smashhit			
Active	back 1337/tcp	registry.atosresearch.eu:18461/smashhit/back:0.3.7 1 Pod / Created a year ago / Pod Restarts: 10	1
Active	front 80/http	registry.atosresearch.eu:18461/smashhit/front:2.0.2 1 Pod / Created a year ago / Pod Restarts: 0	1
Active	idm 80/http, 3000/tcp	registry.atosresearch.eu:18461/smashhit/cross-idm:latest 1 Pod / Created 7 months ago / Pod Restarts: 0	1
Active	mongodb	mongo:4.4.4 1 Pod / Created a year ago / Pod Restarts: 3	1
Active	mysql	registry.atosresearch.eu:18461/smashhit/cross-mysql:latest 1 Pod / Created 7 months ago / Pod Restarts: 0	1
Active	pep-proxy /api	registry.atosresearch.eu:18461/smashhit/cross-pep-proxy:latest 1 Pod / Created a year ago / Pod Restarts: 0	1
Active	pep-proxy-dev /api	registry.atosresearch.eu:18461/smashhit/cross-pep-proxy:latest 1 Pod / Created a year ago / Pod Restarts: 0	1
Active	swagger /swagger	swaggerapi/swagger-ui:v4.12.0 1 Pod / Created a year ago / Pod Restarts: 0	1

Figure 10: smashHit Deployed Workloads

Service discovery

Each workload must define a service discovery entry which configures the networking of the pods (usually the ports to use and the network driver). The figure below shows the service configuration for smashHit. The strategy used in this deployment is to only expose components internally, so for example, the databases are not reachable from the public internet but rather by other smashHit components in the cluster only. Instead, only selected workloads are exposed through an ingress controller, as described in the next section.

State	Name	Type	Target
Active	back Cluster IP: 10.43.151.69	Selector	app-back
Active	front Cluster IP: 10.43.40.16	Selector	app-front
Active	idm Cluster IP: 10.43.31.123	Selector	app-idm
Active	mongodb Cluster IP: 10.43.230.177	Selector	app-mongodb
Active	mysql Cluster IP: 10.43.211.217	Selector	app-mysql
Active	pep-proxy Cluster IP: 10.43.96.115	Selector	app-pep-proxy
Active	pep-proxy-dev Cluster IP: 10.43.213.240	Selector	app-pep-proxy-dev
Active	swagger Cluster IP: 10.43.170.197	Selector	app-swagger

Figure 11: smashHit Service Discovery configuration

Load balancing

Another component included in the architecture of the smashHit framework is an Ingress⁴ load balancer to expose HTTPS routes from outside the cluster to services within the cluster, allowing traffic routing, traffic load balancing, SSL / TLS termination, and offer name-based virtual hosting. Figure below shows the Ingress configuration exposing the IdM service, the smashHit web application, the smashHit API (through a pep-proxy) and the swagger server of the smashHit API specification.

State	Name	Targets	Created
Active	ingress L7 Ingress	idm-smashhit.ari-mobility.eu / > idm smashhit.ari-mobility.eu / > front smashhit.ari-mobility.eu/swagger > swagger smashhit.ari-mobility.eu/api > pep-proxy dev-api-smashhit.ari-mobility.eu/api > pep-proxy-dev	03/29/2021

Figure 12: smashHit Load Balancer Configuration

Database Volumes

In order to maintain data between workload restart, rescheduling or even upgrades, all databases are backed by persistent volumes, as it can be seen in the figure below.

⁴ <https://www.nginx.com/resources/glossary/kubernetes-ingress-controller/>

The screenshot shows the 'Volumes' page in the smashHit dashboard. The page includes a navigation bar with 'Resources', 'Apps', 'Namespaces', 'Members', and 'Tools'. Below the navigation bar, there are tabs for 'Workloads', 'Load Balancing', 'Service Discovery', and 'Volumes'. A search bar and buttons for 'Import YAML' and 'Add Volume' are also present. The main content area displays a table of Persistent Volume Claims (PVCs) in the 'smashhit' namespace. The table has columns for 'State', 'Claim Name', 'Size', 'Persistent Volume', and 'Storage Class'. Two PVCs are listed: 'mongodb-pv-claim' and 'mysql-pv-claim', both with a size of 10 GiB and associated with 'mongodb-volume' and 'mysql-volume' respectively. Both are in a 'Bound' state.

State	Claim Name	Size	Persistent Volume	Storage Class
Namespace: smashhit				
Bound	mongodb-pv-claim	10 GiB	mongodb-volume	-
Bound	mysql-pv-claim	10 GiB	mysql-volume	-

Figure 13: smashHit Volumes

Context-Sensitive Security and Privacy administration

This guide to the smashHit context-sensitive security & privacy (S&P) policies and mechanisms is for platform administrators. The S&P mechanisms consist of three main components: Policy Tool, Policy Server and Event Processing Point (EPP), the latter running as part of the Policy Server. These components provide support for the creation, testing, deployment in the smashHit platform, and support for the enforcement of S&P policies in the smashHit ecosystem. The primary use of the S&P mechanisms is by other components of the smashHit platform, such as the Automatic Contracting Tool. Developers of smashHit components determine how the S&P policies and mechanisms are to be used, and when and how S&P is to be run within the smashHit platform. As an internally used component of the smashHit platform the S&P mechanisms do not have their own GUI though they can and do provide support to applications that do have a GUI.

Initialization of local definitions

Beyond the organizing principles and syntax of the Declarative Policy Language for Privacy (DPLP) that is provided by the S&P mechanisms, a considerable portion of an S&P policy is dependent on domain-specific concepts, vocabulary and relationships from the operational environment. The smashHit Core ontology identifies and defines such information for the smashHit context for the business cases currently addressed.

The S&P system does not have the definition of ontology concept instances built-in but allows these to be provided as a “definitions policy” which is a parameter of a DPLP policy. It is the joint responsibility of the developers and the platform administrator to assure that the appropriate definitions policy is loaded into the Policy Server before policies needing the definitions are constructed.

The developers should determine the appropriate set of terms to be included in the definitions policy and the platform administrator should assure that the definitions policy is loaded. The loading could be part of the initialization script for the S&P mechanisms. First it is necessary to assure that the appropriate definitions policy is available and has been rendered from the smashHit Core ontology in the necessary format. If necessary, the definitions policy could be hand coded but ideally it would be generated automatically from the authoritative ontology. In smashHit responsibility has been assigned to the ontology/context system to generate these definitions in the policy syntax required by the S&P system.

For smashHit S&P policies the definitions policy identifies the elements of the purpose hierarchy, data processing operation hierarchy, and personal data category hierarchy. Each hierarchy may have a “flat” structure where each of the members is assigned only to the category name, e.g. “data processing operation”. Instances of the category may then be compared with the equality relation.

Alternatively, some elements may be assigned to the category name, and the remaining elements assigned in turn to these in a hierarchical fashion.

Instances of the category may then be compared with a “dominates” relation that evaluates to true if there is a sequence of one or more assigns that leads from the second argument of the relation to the first argument. Otherwise, the relation evaluates to false.

The resulting definition policy that defines the members and structure of purpose, data processing operation, and personal data category sets can be loaded in one of several ways into the Policy Server to be available for reference when ordinary DPLP policies are defined:

- built in to the policies.pl file that resides in the server’s source code,
- placed in a distinct file that is dynamically loaded during the system startup sequence by invocation of the paapi/load endpoint,

- loaded dynamically as an argument to the paapi/load endpoint,
- built up dynamically and incrementally by a sequence of invocations of the paapi/add endpoint.

The chosen method will depend on how policies are generally managed in the operational environment.

Operational policy management, backup and recovery

Policy management is an issue that must be considered relative to how the S&P mechanisms are used within a system. S&P does not itself provide policy persistence.

If, on the one hand, the security policies that are to be used for policy decisions within S&P are relatively static and determined by processes outside of S&P then the policies can be loaded when S&P is initialized. If the system is shut down and restarted the policies will need to be reloaded as part of system initialization or as part of a restart of the S&P mechanisms. If, on the other hand, the security policies used within S&P are dynamically created and are actively changing during a run of the S&P system, such that S&P holds the primary, or sole, copy of the policy then a strategy is needed to carry over the policy state from one execution session to another.

One way of doing this would be to save the policy from the running server, store it in a file, and use the file to restore the policy after the S&P server is started. Another way of doing this is to have the system components that use the S&P server to keep track of the state of the information needed to build the policy in their own persistent store, and to rebuild the policy to that state after the S&P server is started.

In smashHit, the information that comprises policy elements originates with other smashHit components, nor does S&P provide the primary storage of that information. Policies are built and referenced as needed by other smashHit components to provide low-level policy comparisons and compliance decisions. When the smashHit platform is started, and with it the S&P Policy Server, the administrative startup procedures must be designed to work together with the smashHit components to establish the desired state of the S&P policy from information in the ACT's graph database, the Context system, and the smashHit ontology tools.

Authorization to use S&P interfaces

The S&P Policy Server offers unprotected interfaces (such as the policy query APIs) for operations that have no side-effects on the state of the Policy Server (though they may leave entries in the security audit trail). Protected interfaces (such as the policy administration APIs) are provided for operations that can change the configuration state of the Server including its policy store or options that control its operation (such as the policy administration APIs).

The protected interfaces require that a token be presented with each protected API call. The token is a secret chosen by the administrator for one or more execution sessions of the Policy Server and shared with the components using the Server that are authorized to call the protected APIs. The administrator assigns the chosen token to the Policy Server as a command line option when the Server is started and this token will be in force for the duration of this execution session. It is then provided to the applications needing it for the current execution. It is recommended that the using applications can accept the value of this token as a startup argument. The token may be changed on a schedule chosen by the administrator and given to the initialization procedures to give to the Server and applications.

Starting the Policy Server

The S&P Policy Server is started as part of the smashHit platform startup procedure. The S&P Event Processing Point runs as part of the Policy Server. The policy server accepts certain command line options when it is invoked. These options are described in D4.4 Section 5.5.2.1.1. The default values for certain options has been changed for simplicity, viz., `--epp` and `--jsonresp` are True by default. As noted previously, the `--token` option is likely to be used. Other options that are likely to be used are those specifying the URL of the Context system (`--context`) and the port numbers for the policy query interface (`--pqport`), the policy administration interface (`--paport`), or both query and admin the same port (`--port`). The `--load` or `--policy` option is one way of loading a single policy, such as a definitions policy, at startup.

F.A.Q.

smashHit platform

Q: What is the smashHit platform?

A: smashHit is a platform that provides a generic, transparent way to view and manage consent supported by disrupting technologies such as traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owner, data provider, and service providers.

Q: Can administrators manually register new users?

A: On the one hand, organization users have their own dedicated registration request flow as described in the “Organization registration” section.

Data owner registration, on the other hand, is not open to the public, but is instead meant to be integrated through the smashHit API by the organizations’ applications themselves (see the data provider/processor developer guide for more details).

That being said, while it is not directly supported or intended through the GUI, administrator users are authorized to utilize the necessary smashHit API endpoints to manually manage data owner accounts, in case it is necessary to provide advanced support.

Q: How can an administrator supervise and manage consents?

A: Consents are only directly visible to the data subjects and the organization(s) directly involved in the processing of data (please refer to the appropriate data owner/developer guidelines for details).

That being said, in the event that support actions require the administrator to review a specific item, the administrator user could use its privileged role to make specific queries to the smashHit APIs to review consent certificates involving a given data subject, organizations, dates, etc.

Glossary

Agent: Entity that bears some form of responsibility in the context of a consent

Administrator: smashHit platform system administrator

Consent: As per Article 4(11) of the GDPR, 'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her

Consent template: A template defining the details of a data processing by an Agent (smashHit organization user), such as the purpose of the processing or the personal data to be processed

CSS: Context sensitivity solution

Data owner: smashHit user role which acts as the data subject according to GDPR

DPL: Declarative Policy Language

DUT: Data Use Traceability

ERL: Event response language

GDPR: Abbreviation for 'General Data Protection Regulation', a legal norm on EU level adopted in 2016, which is directly applicable within its scope and lays down rules for the processing of personal data so as to protect natural persons' fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data

Personal data: Any information which are related to an identified or identifiable natural person (Art. 4 (1) GDPR), e.g. a name or a home address

Purpose: The purpose of Data Handling/Processing

S&P: Security and privacy module

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➤ **Our vision** - Solving Consumer Consent & Data Security for Connected Car and Smart City

➤ **Further information**

This document is part of the smashHit Methodology. The complete set of documents, including other user/developer guides as well as white papers created within this scope can be found on our website:

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6 Annex 4: smashHit Overall Concept White Paper

Smart Dispatcher For Secure And Controlled Sharing Of Distributed
Personal And Industrial Data

smashHit Concept White Paper

October 2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 871477

Foreword

Welcome to our smashHit concept white paper. From the very beginning of the project, we were absolutely convinced that the growing Data Economy has to become more attractive for its key stakeholders (data subjects¹, data providers² and data controllers³) to overcome existing barriers, as e.g. the complicated and time-consuming consent/contract processes, hindering to build-up innovative services using data from multiple sources.

With the growing ability of Consumer Products (CP, such as cars, smart devices, etc.) to generate, gather and share data with third parties among different data-sharing platforms, there will be a general need for flexible and easily manageable procedures to handle data subject's consent and legal rules, to achieve effective and traceable contracting. The complexities of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), for example, possess some challenges and require complex mechanisms to obtain, record and manage consent. Also, data subjects are afraid about improper use of their data. The combination of understanding and relating to the value proposition, consumer trust, and complex consent processes, results in a low opt-in rate for connected product data exchange (e.g. data from cars) and prevents the creation of innovative services (e.g. connected vehicle insurance programs, or smart city solutions).

Thus, we have conceptualised the smashHit system solution as a trusted, secure and integrating privacy-by-design reference Framework to simplify the consent/contract process, as well as to enable consent/contract tracing and sharing among multiple data platforms. In addition, smashHit will offer solutions to identify data misuse as well as to support stakeholders in the creation of legally binding contracts.

All along, we have followed the maxim to think about the needs of data subjects and data customers, but also to win CP manufacturers (e.g. car makers) to open up their products, by designing a convincing trustworthy ecosystem.

During the project lifetime we have finalized the smashHit system concept, its detailed specification and development by our software and RTD development partners and created a working prototype capable of scale. Several public presentations of our smashHit system concept and results have been presented (see smashHit project website).

In this report you will find some more details about the smashHit system concept as a whole, leading from today's constraints in consent/contract processes to how smashHit is facing those challenges with its innovative trusted and secure system concept.

If you got curious about how all that is made possible, just continue on the following pages, enjoy the reading, and please contact us with your feedback or questions!

- smashHit support email: info@smashhit.eu
- smashHit project website: <https://smashhit.eu>

¹ The person to whom the data relates to. The term is a legal attribute (Art. 4 Nr. 1 GDPR). The data subject can be the device owner at the same time. If the data relates to another person (e.g. the co-driver/another passenger) then the device owner is not the data subject. In this case the data subject will be e.g. the co-driver/the other passenger

² Data provider application and user: They get the consent to collect data from user devices according to the user consent

³ A legal or natural person, an agency, a public authority, or any other body who, alone or when joined with others, determines the purposes of any personal data and the means of processing it

Executive Summary

The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data subject consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators. The Framework will provide methods and tools, such as the smashHit Platform.

The following key points will refer to those main innovative features and show the high future potential of the smashHit framework concept:

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1 Challenges on the way to build a framework for assuring trusted and secure sharing of data streams

The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, which block business opportunities due to inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data sharing platforms actors and operators. The Framework provides methods and tools, such as the smashHit platform, to assure common consent over data shared by using semantic models of consent and legal rules. The new tools include consent management and automatic contracting among the data subjects, data providers, service providers and users. It also includes traceability of use of data.

These tools are critical for enormous volumes on data streaming from the usage of mass products with cyber physical features (e.g. vehicles). These data streams offer new opportunities to build innovative services, but their combination with other personal and industrial data is subject to complex ownership and consent aspects, data streaming from these products might be considered as personal data and there are many different and partially conflicting interests involved regarding the use of data generated by the use of such products. The project has been based on the solutions developed in previous projects (AutoMat, Cross-CPP, CAMPANEO, DALICC etc.). smashHit is driven by two industrial Business Cases involving several existing industrial and personal data platforms owned by the leading data providers in three diverse sectors (automotive industry, insurance, and smart city). Demonstrators of various applications of the developed solutions are being developed and will be shown latest from end of the project on.

The smashHit project vision as well as a range of selected key problems and needs in the state-of-the-art solution for consent and contract handling in the data economy led to the starting point of the smashHit project. Driven by these needs, innovative approaches were compiled to build the smashHit architecture as key element of the project.

1.1 Motivation

In the last years many data sharing platform approaches for different purposes (like B2B data exchange, data marketplaces or data processing services) emerged, giving cross-sectorial industries access to the great spectrum of sensor data coming from high volume products from various industrial sectors (vehicles, smart home devices, smart cities data etc.). With the increasing number of connected sensors and actuators within such mass products (so called cyber physical products), this number will rise exponentially in short-term. This enormous amount of data offered by various data sharing platforms represent:

- a massive information resource to create new value, allowing the improvement of existing services or the establishment of diverse new innovative services, by combining data streams from various sources
- a major big data-driven business potential, not only for the manufacturers of Consumer Products (CP), but in particular also for cross-sectorial industries and various organisations with interdisciplinary applications

The majority of these data sharing platform approaches offer a scalable, secure and trusted sharing of data. However, they all lack in the provision of solutions for consent creation, management and observation between two or more involved actors that aim to share personal data. To fully exploit data sharing approaches in practice, they have to consider national and international laws like the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Among others, such regulations define that data subjects can decide by whom and for which purposes their data can be used;

they define how data providers have to handle data and they define how data have to be processed. A data sharing platform that considers such regulations needs an additional layer of consent creation linked to a contract which would guarantee the compliance with all requirements of the contracting parties and national and international laws. This gap needs to be filled and is where smashHit aims to bring an added value.

1.2 Challenges & Steps towards the smashHit Framework Solution

As mentioned above, the rapid growth of the Data Economy is also reflected on the number of B2B, B2C and B2G data-sharing platforms recently launched, which are contributing to fragment the market, preventing business opportunities due to lack of interoperability, inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators.

There is a short-term challenge for the data economy to look for an interoperable data-sharing platform to enforce and manage multi-platform agreements for exchanging data whilst protecting and assuring compliance with GDPR, Privacy and Security Policy enforcement rules of individual data providers, national (country) data privacy and protection rules and EU-legal directives and legislation surrounding personal and industrial data generation, storage and sharing. Due to this high level of market fragmentation, the situation today is characterized by far too complex and individual value chains resulting in economic inefficiency. Therefore, the use and integration of data from various platforms is limited due to missing solutions for agreement on consent, legal rules, effective contracting, data use traceability, security & privacy issues etc.

The requirement analysis at the beginning of the project has shown that this situation is mainly characterised by the following major challenges and barriers for all stakeholders in the value chain, the service providers (data processors) and for the CP manufacturers (data providers) and the CP owners (data subjects):

- The number of steps required to gain consent create customer “friction”.
- Time taken to obtain the required consent is too long.
- Verifying a person giving consent is often insufficient as well as duplicated at each consent step.
- Problem of broken consent chain is unsolved.
- Lack of tools to prevent data misuse prevent willingness of data providers to provide data.
- Insufficient control for data subjects over their data.
- Missing support in creating legally binding contracts.

In contrast to today's fragmented data sharing landscape, which is characterised by non-heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations and by this means is hindering the use and integration of data from various platforms due to missing solutions for effective consent/contracting and data use traceability etc., the smashHit project focuses on user-oriented solutions that make data marketplaces more attractive and trustful for its key stakeholders. Therefore, smashHit has to overcome several obstacles by establishing an inter-data-platform solution enabling simplified multi-platform consent/contract processes for exchanging data also ensuring a trustful data use traceability. To achieve these key challenges, smashHit needed to develop the following main characteristics:

- ✓ **Improve citizens trust** by means of tracing the use of data over diverse platforms
- ✓ **Improve OEM & data customer's trust** by means of fingerprinted data to ensure traceability/unchangeability along value chain and data quality, as well as consent tracing -> notification of all involved contractors in case of broken consent chain
- ✓ **Simplify consent process** through authentication of the individual (certification of consent) and single point of consent (management and distribution of consent)
- ✓ **Support in consent/contract generation** by supporting the digital creation of contract texts, and taking relevant legislations/legal rules into account

Such an innovative inter-data-platform platform solution will have several positive effects on the European Data Economy, as e.g.:

- To overcome existing barriers, as e.g. the complicated and time-consuming consent/contract processes
- Increase trust for all stakeholders in the data market, due to a strong data traceability mechanism
- Increase willingness of data providers (OEM) to provide CP data for 3rd party use
- Open new opportunities for value-creation by creation of innovative services using data from multiple platforms

Data subjects need a solution that would enable them to easily trace the use of their data over diverse platforms. The solution must provide the data subject the power to manage their data, enabling them to identify for each of their products, who gets which product data, for which purposes they are used and how long is the contract run-time. In addition, the solution has to simplify consent processes, to create the trust and motivate the users to share their data by offering solutions users find useful and necessary.

Data providers (e.g. OEMs) need a solution that allows to identify the origin of a data leakage in case of data misuse in an efficient way. Further they need to have the possibility to monitor if given consent is broken. Both cases have a high risk of reputation damage for the data provider.

Generally, we can state, that a reliable solution to eliminate the above data traceability challenges related with the 'reconstruction of data leakage' and minimisation of 'reputation damage risks' will considerably increase the willingness of large CP manufacturers to provide more data from their products.

Data controllers as the processors of the data subject's data are offering services based on data from various data platforms. A key request for them is to simplify the process to obtain consent and easy contracting. Moreover, data controllers have similar needs w.r.t. data traceability as described for data providers, e.g. regarding identification of broken consent chain or backtracking of data misuse.

Service customers have similar need as the data subjects, and may even be considered as data subjects for most situations, as e.g. simplified consent/contract processes and a clear traceability of data usage for all their products.

Finally, **Legislators** need a solution which enables to apply their laws in a technical way. A unified solution would also simplify the controlling of law compliance in the data economy.

2 The smashHit Framework Solution to meet the challenges

smashHit started with the aim to design and implement a trusted, secure- and privacy-by-design reference platform to simplify the consent/contract process as well as to enable consent tracing and sharing among multiple data platforms, as well as offering solutions to identify data misuse as well as to support data customers in creating contract documents. The solution addresses the identified needs of different actors in the data economy. Therefore, smashHit provides answers for these needs compiled in the shape of a smashHit Platform which can be divided into five different main building blocks shown in the following figure, which build the **key innovations** of the project. These building blocks are partly using basic concepts of state-of-the-art technologies that can be used for further exploitation to fill the identified gaps.

Figure 1: smashHit framework solution conceptual module overview

2.1 smashHit Platform

The smashHit platform module provides the basic functionalities within the overall smashHit framework solution. Different actors aim to get consent creation, management and observation functionalities. In particular it covers the following:

- **User management functions** – This component includes the functionality regarding the life cycle of the actors involved in the smashHit framework. It interacts with the user database which stores information related to user accounts.
- **Semantic model of consent and legal rights** – This component represents the used core ontology and resulting semantic data model for the description of legal rights, consents, context and automatic contracting rules, terms and conditions.
- **Context sensitivity solution** – This component adds context sensitive features to the overall smashHit framework and enables a context dependent behaviour of the system, e.g. monitoring of user preferences.

Figure 2: Consent Certification process

As part of the smashHit platform, the **Consent Certification Module** includes functionalities along the life cycle of consent certificates and is a core component of smashHit. The module includes functionalities for consent management and support. Semantic models are used to describe consent (-chains) between two or more participants. The described consent will be digitally certified and saved in a database. This approach will enable to manage and control consent about data usage with two or more involved participants in the Data Use Traceability module. Figure 2 shows a simplified look at a consent certification process. The actual process is not linear and some steps were simplified (such as the registration process) to make for an easier reading of this paper however it presents a good overview.

2.2 Automatic Contracting

The smashHit solution accelerates the consent creation process to increase the efficiency in the data economy and to reduce the efforts needed for a consent creation and consent management. This component aims to allow a semi-automatic consent form creation process based on compliant data usage and processing rules. This approach is based on ontologies and reasoning technologies (having the smashHit semantic model as basis). Construction and management of contracts based on specific terms and conditions in compliance with GDPR is another service provided by the ACT. It provides a flexible yet meaningful model for data sharing in smart city and insurance domains under different circumstances.

Figure 3: Automatic Contracting Tool component architecture

Data subjects need a solution which provides monitoring functionalities over their data. This is enabled by the consent certification in the previously described module. Certified contracts and consent(-chains), saved in a knowledge graph enables to always have an overview about signed contracts and consents, and enables the tracing of consent, allowing the identification of a broken consent chain.

2.3 Data Use Traceability

The data use traceability component has two purposes: (1st) to trace data flows by applying hashing, fingerprinting/watermarking, and (2nd) the identification of data leakages using the same tools. Those tools are used to make the data recognisable even after some modifications. The component addresses the need of OEMs, data providers and data controllers to get a solution which enables the identification of data leakages or misuses. Basis for this component are data hashing, fingerprinting and watermarking technologies that shall enable the identification of the last data source within the smashHit ecosystem. The data hashing combined with fingerprint or with watermarking provides answers about where the leaked or misused data was located or forwarded the last time which will avoid the blaming of guiltless participants in a consent chain. Figure 4 shows from 1) to 6) an example of how the information flows within all stakeholders of the smashHit ecosystem.

Figure 4: Data Use Traceability component: example of information flow within all stakeholders of the smashHit ecosystem

2.4 Security and Privacy Mechanisms/Metrics

The smashHit Platform is developed and runs in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The principles of privacy by design and by default have been cornerstones for the development of the smashHit infrastructure. The security & privacy policy languages and mechanisms support compliance with security and privacy policies represented and applied within the smashHit platform and connected data processors.

Figure 5: Security and Privacy component architecture

The Security and Privacy mechanisms combine privacy/security policies of data subjects and data controllers/processors in a complementary way. The Policy Server makes policy decisions based

on policy information and context, including consent information gathered through the consent acquisition UI and provided by the ACT through policy administration. As granted by policy decisions, the ACT issues a Consent Certificate that external data processors apply to control access to protected personal information. Events reported to the Security and Privacy Event Processing may provide information to smashHit Data Use Traceability (see Figure 5). Security Metrics assess the smashHit Framework's quality of conformance to governing regulations and other norms.

3 Glossary

ACT: Automatic Contracting Tool

B2B: Business-to-Business

B2C: Business-to-Consumer

B2G: Business-to-Government

Consent: As per Article 4(11) of the GDPR, 'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her

GDPR: Abbreviation for 'General Data Protection Regulation', a legal norm on EU level adopted in 2016, which is directly applicable within its scope and lays down rules for the processing of personal data so as to protect natural persons' fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data

OEM: Original Equipment Manufacturer

Personal data: Any information which are related to an identified or identifiable natural person (GDPR Art.4 (1))

RTD: Research and Technological Development

UI: (Contracting) User Interface

➤ **Our vision** - Solving Consumer Consent & Data Security for Connected Car and Smart City

➤ **Further information**

This document is part of the smashHit Methodology. The complete set of documents, including user/developer guides as well as other white papers created within this scope can be found on our website:

<https://smashhit.eu/publications>

➤ **Our consortium**

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7 Annex 5: smashHit Semantic Model Technical Essay

Smart Dispatcher For Secure And Controlled Sharing Of Distributed Personal And Industrial Data

smashHit Semantic Model

Technical Essay

October 2022

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Executive Summary

The objective of smashHit is to assure trusted and secure sharing of data streams from both personal and industrial platforms, needed to build sectorial and cross-sectorial services, by establishing a Framework for processing of data owner consent and legal rules and effective contracting, as well as joint security and privacy preserving mechanisms. The vision of smashHit is to overcome obstacles in the rapidly growing Data Economy which is characterized by heterogeneous technical designs and proprietary implementations, locking business opportunities due to the inconsistent consent and legal rules among different data-sharing platforms actors and operators. The Framework provides methods and tools, such as the smashHit platform or Automatic Contracting tool.

The following key points refer to those main innovative features brought to the smashHit Framework by the developed smashHit Semantic Model:

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If you got curious about how all that is made possible, just continue on the following pages, enjoy the reading, and please contact us with your feedback or questions!

- smashHit support email: info@smashhit.eu
- smashHit project website: <https://smashhit.eu>

1 Motivation

The smashHit semantic model is one of the core components of the smashHit project and facilitates communication between other smashHit components, offering numerous benefits. However, before diving into detail, let's first understand the problem.

While the problem definition can be presented formally (or technically), we decided to introduce it in general layman terminology so that even those who are not technical will also get a glimpse of what we are solving and why we are doing it this way. Let us say that you own a few big fields. It does not matter how many big fields, you can assume as many as you would like. The key point here is to have fields that a single person cannot manage. You then hire, say 10 people, with the help of recruitment companies. These hired 10 people are from different regions of the world and speak different languages and have different cultural and societal backgrounds. Even though, if we were to assume, that they speak some common languages, there exist different challenges. The first challenge is related to the semantics of the communication between you, the employer, and the employee. Since the employees are from different societal and cultural backgrounds, they might understand differently of things that you wanted to communicate. The second challenge is the cooperation between the employees among each other. There are the well-known multilingual environments problems.

Now, at this point, you might be wondering, what has this thing to do with software or semantic model? What if we tell you, it is not only related to software problem but also the problem that we are solving using the semantic model. If you are thinking is this project about technology, how can multilingual environment relate to software, then you are not wrong. All we discussed is about people, language and field and said this is what we are solving and nothing about technology. Let us help you here with how the analogy of this people, field and language is related to what we are doing. The first challenge that we specified above is relating to the semantics of communication between the employer and employee. The same problem exists in the software as well. If two or more software modules do not communicate in a same common language with common semantics, then they don't work well, they fail or system breaks. It follows that we need something standardised. The second challenges that we specified above is about co-operation between the employees from different background itself. In software, we refer to this kind of problem as interoperability problem. Again, to solve this, we need standardisation. Semantic models, especially in the form of ontology, such as what is developed as a part of smashHit project does exactly this task, which is (i) to provide the standardised semantics for all software components and (ii) to facilitate interoperability. If we have to say in technical terminology, the semantic models provide the formalisation of the real-world concepts in a machine-readable format, thereby enabling the interoperability. The concepts in the case of this project are about the GDPR and data processing as for example, consent and the different types of data processing activities. The smashHit semantic model provides a standardised vocabulary that can not only be used in this project but in any other related project with similar scope.

Following up on the challenges mentioned above, and coming back to fields again, when there's a difficulty in communication and co-operation: for any task you might have to refer back to employee and employer multiple times, i.e., there will be multiple to-and-fro communications. This in terms of software can be related to the IO (Input-Output) operations. If there are many IO operations then it creates a dependency problem and is difficult to scale. This is another challenge that semantic models help in solving, partly or completely.

2 Designing Semantic Models

Following the motivation for the use of ontologies in our project, when designing the smashHit core semantic model we were faced with several challenges, which can be summarized by the following:

- There are already many ontologies that exist regarding consent, contract, privacy, and legal rights but none that models all topics.
- To determine whether we create a new ontology from scratch or extend the previous ones.
- Defining the main classes and subclasses for consent, contract, tracing, and tracking in the process of data provision and data consumption/use.
- The overall design of the data workflow in application use cases (e.g. in the smart cities and insurance domains).
- To define the relationship between classes to provide identification of the leakage of data and audit-proof logging of transactions.

The rest of the details, such as the use cases where it is applied and the results achieved will be explained in the subsequent sections.

In order to overcome the challenges described above, we have followed best practices for the reuse of existing work in ontology engineering. We have investigated several existing ontologies and integrated published vocabularies, taxonomies and ontologies into the smashHit semantic model, from now on also mentioned as smashHit core ontology. For cases, where existing and integrated ontologies for modelling smashHit were incomplete, these ontologies were extended. The approach of the semantic model development followed was:

- specification of the main concepts to be used, coming from the smashHit components.
Note: the analysis of the already existing ontologies was made in parallel, overtaking said concepts from these ontologies.
- specification of the sub-classes for them (either reusing from the identified ontologies or from scratch)
- specification of the relationships (either reusing from the identified ontologies or from scratch)
- Verify that all requirements of the identified project use cases are covered within the smashHit Core ontology and make improvements as necessary
- iterate and add more details
- revisit and check the completeness of the ontology with the business cases' consent processes
- iterate and add more details

The mentioned external ontologies and vocabularies that were identified for reuse are: *GConsent*¹, *DPV*², *DCAT*³, *FIBO:Contract*⁴, *OntoSensor*⁵, *Prov-o*⁷, *CampaNeo*⁸ and *Languages, Countries, and Codes (LCC)*⁹.

The smashHit Core ontology contains the main smashHit concepts in the fields of:

- User identification such as *Agents* (including *Person* and *Organisation*) and respective identification categories (*PersonalDataCategory* which includes concepts such as *Name* or *Address*), see .
- Data identification such as *Metadata* or *Sector* which is a very important entity being the main identification and connection point to the data for which the data subjects will provide consent.
- Consent/Contract declarations such as *Consent*, *Contract*, *Status* and *Processing* (see Figure 2-2 and Figure 2-3)
- Description of the privacy context, expressed by such as *Purpose* and *Risk*.

Figure 2-1 shows the main entities overview of the smashHit Core ontology. In addition to these entities, relationships were also modelled in order to be able to relate entities, and later on, to model complex structures like the one we need to model a consent template and its use in the Automatic Contracting knowledge graph (see below in this paper). Also, the data identification entity *Metadata* connects to other entities such as *Resource* and *SensorDataCategory* for further categorization of the data in question.

¹ H. J. Pandit, C. Debruyne und P. McBennett, *GConsent*, A consent ontology based on the GDPR, ADAPT Centre, (Trinity College Dublin). DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-21348-0_18

² H. J. Pandit, D. O'Sullivan und D. Lewis, „An Ontology Design Pattern for Describing Personal Data in Privacy Policies”, in: Proceedings of the 9th Workshop on Ontology Design and Patterns (WOP 2018), 2018.

³ <https://www.w3.org/community/dpvcg/wiki/>

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

⁵ <https://edmcouncil.org/general/custom.asp?page=AboutFIBO4>

⁶ <https://mmisw.org/ont/univmemphis/sensor#>

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

⁸ https://www.digitale-technologien.de/DT/Redaktion/EN/Standardartikel/Smarte_Datenwirtschaft/Projekte/SDW_campaNeo_en.html

⁹ <https://www.omg.org/spec/LCC/1.2/About-LCC/>

Figure 2-1: smashHit Core ontology main concepts overview

Figure 2-2: Overview of the class *Consent* and the classes related to it in smashHit Core ontology

Figure 2-3: Overview of the class *Contract* and the classes related to it in smashHit Core ontology

One of the main issues that we faced while developing the smashHit semantic model was how to improve interoperability with other ontologies used in the same area. To do this, we studied the possibility of relating the ontology with an existing top-level ontology (TLO), such as *BFO* or *DOLCE*. The conclusion at the time of the project was that no TLO in particular would be used. The reasons for this decision were: on the one hand none of the reused ontologies is based on a TLO, therefore there is no guidance in selecting one in particular in the same smashHit core topics, and that would best fit the purpose of the smashHit Core semantic model and on the other hand, the short time in which the smashHit Core ontology was needed for use.

Therefore, the decision was not to select and use a TLO in particular. Instead, we decided to follow good ontology design practices that will lead to a simple and structured ontology, which can be aligned to a TLO for interoperability and standardization purposes in the future. These ontology design principles are derived from the *Basic Formal Ontology TLO*¹⁰ and are extended and adapted for the smashHit Core ontology:

- Use single nouns and avoid acronyms
- Ensure univocity (univocal = having one meaning only) of terms and relational expressions
- Distinguish the general from particular
- Provide all non-root terms with definitions (*dct:description*)
- Use essential features in defining terms and avoid circularity
- Start with the most general terms in the domain
- Use simpler terms than the term you are defining (to ensure intelligibility)
- Do not create terms for universals through logical combination
- Structure ontology around *is_a hierarchy* and ensure *is_a* completeness

¹⁰ R. Arp, B. Smith and A. D. Spear, Building Ontologies with Basic Formal Ontology, The MIT Press, 2015

Main assumption is that the smashHit Core ontology focuses on consent, contracts, data processing etc. All associated concepts needed to follow the consent life cycle from request up to revocation¹¹.

These design guidelines and assumption have allowed for improved overall consistency (hierarchically) by analysing and restructuring the entities, analysis and provision of sound and consistent definitions to all entities and data properties, and overall, errors identification and correction.

One of the best practices for ontology engineering that was followed while developing the smashHit Core ontology is the documentation of the entities imported or created. Documentation is made in two steps, the first is when entities are added to the ontology, they need to have a description for the term, and the second, is using a tool to create documentation that can be consulted at any time. The tool used was *WIDOCO*¹² which uses *LODE*¹³ (Life OWL Documentation Environment), with some further customisation, to create the smashHit Core documentation. The current version of the smashHit Core ontology documentation can be seen under:

<https://smashhiteu.github.io/smashHitCoreV1>

¹¹ A. Kurteva, T. R. Chhetri, H. J. Pandit and A. Fensel, “Consent through the Lens of Semantics: State of the Art Survey and Best Practices,” *Semantic Web*, p. 1 – 27, 1 January 2021

¹² <https://github.com/dgarijo/Widoco>

¹³ <https://essepuntato.it/lode/>

3 Application of Semantic Models

3.1 Standardised representation of consent and contract

As we described in the introduction section, our solution is based on semantic technology, such as ontology. But what is a semantic model, and how is it beneficial compared with other data models like databases? A semantic model can be defined as the development of descriptions and representations of data in such a way that the latter's meaning is explicit, accurate, and commonly understood by both humans and computer systems. This definition encompasses a wide range of data artefacts, including metadata schemas, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, ontologies, knowledge graphs, entity-relationship (E-R) models, property graphs, and other conceptual models for data representation. It represents the implicit meaning of the data by specifying the concepts and the relationships within the data. Information sources, such as relational databases contain a tremendous amount of structured data that can be leveraged to build and augment knowledge graphs. However, they rarely provide a semantic model to describe their contents.

For illustration, we take databases as an example of building data models. Later, we will compare it with semantic modelling. Creating a suitable data model in databases requires at least the following steps: (i) defining the purpose of the data. (ii) a proper normalisation of the data. (iii) reducing the redundancy. (iv) a proper naming convention. (v) to define constraint integrity properly. Due to this complexity, we can say that the data modelling process in databases is very complex. While creating semantic models on the other hand, is very simple. The ontology is used as a data model to create a semantic model by creating relationships between data when the data is organised. The data is organized into three essential parts—the first data element or subject, the relationship, and then the second data element or object. We can create classes, properties, and object properties with their relationships in ontology. Humans and machines commonly understood this semantic model. Further, the semantic model can aid the building of common solutions, foster interoperability, support knowledge discovery, and decision making. Following this, we created the semantic models for consent and contracts in the smashHit Core ontology.

The semantic model of consent is constructed as defined by GDPR's requirements (Article 7, Recital 32). In order to represent and store informed consent semantically within the knowledge graph (KG), the schema of the smashHit Core ontology has been followed. A KG instance of consent (graphical visualisation) is shown in Figure 3-1. The nodes of the graph represent the actual values, whereas the edges denote the relationship between nodes. The node with red colour is said to be a focus node and arrows from the focus node to other nodes describe the relationship between those nodes. For example, the arrow from the focus node to Tyrol denotes the relationship between consent and state — the location where the consent is granted. Similar, *hasDataController* represents a relationship between consent and the data controller.

The smashHit Core ontology goes beyond consent and addresses contract, which is another GDPR legal basis for data processing in smart cities and insurance domains. The main challenge is to bind GDPR rights with businesses, specifically in the form of digital semantic contracts. This creates an opportunity for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to manage personal data in contracting services on scale. Our contracting solution is built in collaboration with both industry and legal experts. An instance of contract in the knowledge graph is presented in Figure 3-2.

To illustrate data processing between a data controller and a data processor in the smashHit, let us assume LexisNexis acts as a data controller and Infotripla Oy acts as a data processor (according to GDPR). In data processing where a contract is required, they must satisfy the requirements defined by GDPR (e.g., Art. 28, 32).

[5cf187194c989156427141951c47b5b2de53f1b3b8cea2f2e754edc01bf686ef](#)

5cf187194c989156427141951c47b5b2de53f1b3b8cea2f2e754edc01bf686ef

Types:

:ConsentID

RDF rank:

0

:GrantedAtTime

2021-05-21T09:03:31.859000+00:00

:hasExpiry

2021-05-21T09:03:31.859000+00:00

Figure 3-1: Knowledge graph instance of consent (graphical visualisation)

For instance, the data processor must notify the data controller if there is a breach of a contract. The insurers can view the information about the data storage and its usage.

[contb2b_e45dc546-2e9e-11ed-be7d-3f8589292a29](#)

contb2b_e45dc546-2e9e-11ed-be7d-3f8589292a29

Types:

owl:NamedIndividual

fibc-fnd-agr-ctr:Contract

RDF rank:

0

Search instance properties

:consentID

:contractID

contb2b_e45dc546-2e9e-11ed-be7d-3f8589292a29

:forPurpose

data processing agreement between LexisNexis and FVH data processor

:hasContext

online

:hasEndDate

2023-07-07 10:38:07.617000+00:00 xsd:dateTime

identifier

Show 1 more

:inMedium

online

Figure 3-2: Knowledge graph instance of contract (graphical visualisation).

Figure 3-2 represents a B2B (business-to-business) contract between a data controller and a data processor. The central red node represents the focus node, while other red nodes denote the collection of values. For instance, the focus node has a relationship (has a contract category) with category business to business. It also shows the contract has a relationship with terms and conditions, which have a relationship with obligations.

3.2 Automatic Contracting Tool

Once the semantic models of consent and contracts are constructed, the next question could be how we can use these models in the real world to test their applicability. In smashHit, the Automatic Contracting Tool (ACT) supports the automatic generation of consent documents and execution of contracts based on specific terms and conditions in compliance with GDPR (as is modelled by the smashHit Semantic Model). It is a stand-alone module, which could be reused by any of the smashHit components or by external service providers via an API. The ACT provides the following functionalities:

- Semi-automatic consent/contract creation and annotation in the legal knowledge graph based on smart cities and insurance domains.
- Semi-automatic consent status update, namely, consent granting and revocation.
- Automatic GDPR compliant consent/contract document generation.
- Consent and contract modelling, specifically terms and conditions with knowledge graphs.
- Compliance verification in the case of a broken consent chain and contract breaches.
- Traceability of consent and contracts within the KG via relationships between concepts.
- Contracting User Interface (UI).
- B2C and B2B contracts modelling and implementations.

3.3 Data Use Traceability

Another application of the semantic model is the Data Use Traceability component. The Data Use Traceability component facilitates the tracing and tracking of data, in order to secure personal and industrial data sharing among companies and provide transparency to the data subject. Moreover, the Data Use Traceability component also tackles the risk of data leakage. For example, data can be fingerprinted or watermarked to enable re-identification of this data in case of a data leak. To provide the functionalities, we defined the classes and properties for Data Use traceability within smashHit Core ontology. We extended existing ontologies on data traceability reusing common properties and adding new ones, specific to our use case. We added new classes fingerprint, hash, and watermark specified in the semantic model as subclasses of processing class. We then added the properties *has description*, *has method*, and *has parameter* to the processing class. We also added properties *has fingerprint*, *has hash*, *has watermark* to the resource class. Thus, the semantic model can provide a common understanding of the concepts used in the Data Use Traceability component.

3.4 Context Sensitivity Solution

The Context Sensitivity Solution allows data subjects to configure context sensitive options associated with the active consents, which will be monitored continuously during consent's lifetime. Within the UI, the data subject will be offered with some options as seen in the following figure. Here, the user can select their desired context preferences associated with the consents, in which we are making use of the semantic model concepts *Purpose* and *Sector*.

After the new options are processed and stored by the CSS, any existing consents for the user will pass a compliance check to detect any conflicts with the new preferences. Any conflicts detected by the CSS will be reported via email to the data subject, so that they can manually review each of the offending consents and choose if they want to issue a revoke request to the consent.

Figure 3-3: User preferences configuration options

3.5 Consent registration templates

Another application of the smashHit semantic model is in the communication between the external data subjects looking to collect consent for their applications and the smashHit platform. In order to be able to gather consent from data subjects, the data controllers and processors need to first make sure that the consent request and registration is “understood” by the smashHit platform and therefore this application registration follows a template that is compliant with the smashHit Core ontology, i.e. as shown before a consent request has mandatory fields (see Figure 2-2 and an example in Figure 3-1) and these are followed by the external data subjects when planning the communication with the smashHit platform (see Figure 3-4).

smashHit System Administrator admin@smashhit.aif-mobility.eu

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Consent Template Details

ID	62fb60afd201af000a48a693	
NAME	Email address for managing user account and consent information	
CREATED	August 16, 2022 at 11:17:35 AM GMT+2	
ORGANIZATION	[REDACTED]	
PURPOSE	Service Provision	
PURPOSE DESCRIPTION	Your email address is used to manage your user account and the consent information you provide. This information is stored in the smashHit system.	
PERSONAL DATA	CATEGORY	DATA
	feedback	feedback
	Contact	Email Address
SECTOR	Information and Communication	
DATA PROCESSING	Use, Store, Share	
AGENTS	APPLICATION	ROLE
	[REDACTED]	dataController

[Edit Consent Template](#)

Figure 3-4: Example of a data controller consent template for their App

4 Conclusion

From the preceding discussion, it is evident that communication is one of the most challenging aspects, especially for distributed systems. Furthermore, we have learned from the discussion that standardisation is the answer. As demonstrated by the applications of semantic models, semantic models can aid in standardisation and solve communication or interoperability issues between all software modules and stakeholders. However, semantic models present their own set of challenges, and if these challenges are not addressed, the models will not provide any benefits and will instead cause problems.

The following are the key takeaways from this technical essay:

- Semantic models can help with standardised representation of information, thereby helping in addressing the interoperability problem.
- Always follow the best practices while building the semantic model, i.e., ontology. For example, always look for existing information that can be reused and never try to reinvent the wheel.
- Involve all the stakeholders early in the design process and agree on common design principles and conventions. This is even more important when you are dealing with legal stuff, such as GDPR, where the early involvement of a legal team is absolutely necessary.

We were able to show the validity of the developed model, as the smashHit Core ontology was build and tested in the fields addressed by smashHit within two dimensions: i) internally by the smashHit software components using the semantic model as a formal guidance for their internal data model, ii) between the two business cases and the smashHit Framework, i.e. for the sake of modelling the consent templates for three different applications (i.e. in the vehicle insurance and smart city domains).

We are also quite convinced, that the developed smashHit Core Ontology models all relevant elements in the field of consent and contract. This being said, our model can and should be applied in other frameworks and solutions dealing with the same challenges.

5 Glossary

ACT: Automatic Contracting Tool

Agent: Entity that bears some form of responsibility in the context of a consent

B2C: Business-to-Consumer

B2B: Business-to-Business

Consent: As per Article 4(11) of the GDPR, 'consent' of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her

Consent template: A template defining the consent to be requested by a smashHit application, including: purpose, personal data, data processing, and agents

CSS: Context Sensitivity Solution

GDPR: Abbreviation for 'General Data Protection Regulation', a legal norm on EU level adopted in 2016, which is directly applicable within its scope and lays down rules for the processing of personal data so as to protect natural persons' fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data.

KG: Knowledge Graph

Personal data: Any information which are related to an identified or identifiable natural person (GDPR Art.4 (1))

Purpose: The purpose of Data Handling

SMEs: Small and Medium size Enterprises

TLO: Top-Level Ontology – ontology which consists of very general terms that are common across all domains

UI: (Contracting) User Interface

➤ **Our vision** - Solving Consumer Consent & Data Security for Connected Car and Smart City

➤ **Further information**

This document is part of the smashHit Methodology. The complete set of documents, including user/developer guides as well as a concept white paper created within this scope can be found on our website:

<https://smashhit.eu/publications>

➤ **Our consortium**

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the smashHit Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission in the same.

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<https://smashhit.eu>

twitter.com/smashhitp

linkedin.com/company/smashhit

8 Annex 6: smashHit Internal Policies Guidelines

Smart Dispatcher For Secure And Controlled Sharing Of Distributed Personal And Industrial Data

smashHit

Policy Guidelines

smashHit Platform Internal (Legal, Privacy, Consent) Policies Guides

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Introduction

The process/activity related Methodology Guidelines describes regulations in respect to the interaction between the key smashHit Stakeholders with the platform, such as contractual and privacy/security issues.

Purpose

The presented methodology guidelines cover legal, privacy and consent regulations for key processes/activities in respect to the actions/roles of the various stakeholders and their interaction required for the operation of the smashHit platform.

Audience

The methodology guidelines are meant for all stakeholders of the smashHit platform, as well as candidates planning to be a stakeholder.

Scope

The contents of the methodology guidelines will cover regulations in respect to the interaction between the various stakeholders.

The smashHit team does not take responsibility, when not following the instructions given in this guide.

If you find a regulation for which there is no content in this guide you can request it through info@smashhit.eu.

Troubleshooting

For any questions or inquiries about the use of the smashHit platform web application or the contents of it or this guide, or if you find there is no content in this guide for some functionality, please forward it to: info@smashhit.eu

Contact

smashHit Project website: <https://smashhit.eu>

smashHit platform support: info@smashhit.eu

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1. Structure of the Guide

This guide is divided into two main parts. The first part looks at contractual regulations. It is meant to guide those who engage in digital or smart contracts within the infrastructure of smashHit.

The second part focuses on privacy and security issues around the processing of personal data. Here, the smashHit privacy policy is explained. It also contains important notes for data controllers who may wish to interact with the smashHit system.

At the end of this document, some frequently asked questions (FAQs) have been answered for readers, and in the Glossary key terms used within this document that might not be self-explaining or known by every reader are briefly explained.

2. Contractual Regulations

This part is meant to guide those who engage in a digital or smart contract within the smashHit system. A contract is simply an agreement between two or more parties that intend to produce a legally binding effect. Traditionally, a contract is entered into when one party makes an offer, and the other party accepts it. Other legal formalities may apply such as formality relating to the medium through which the contract is evidenced (e.g., in writing), or signature. Although the traditional contracting process is usually concluded manually, advancements in ICT have brought the opportunity to conclude some aspects of the contract process through automated means. This is commonly referred to as a “smart contract”, “digital contract” or “automated contract”.

Despite the technical developments, it is important to note that the digitalisation and automation of contracts has several legal implications and raises several questions such as whether automated execution of some or all aspects of a contract would produce a similar legal effect as a manually executed one; whether similar legal conditions applicable in traditional contracts are present in digital or smart contracts; whether the terminology used in designing digital or smart contracts has the same meaning when interpreted by the courts. At the core of this transition is the question of whether contracting parties seeking to regulate their mutual rights and obligations in a legally binding contract can use computer code (whether fully or partially) for this purpose. Other legal issues may arise relating to, for example, enforcement and termination. Careful consideration of these questions is very important for any actor engaging in smart contracting, particularly because of complying with legal requirements.

In the following, key elements, and requirements of entering a legally binding contractual relationship shall be explained in a nutshell.

2.1. Elements and Validity of a Contract

There is no harmonised contract law at the EU level. The following analysis is mainly based on commonly applicable rules across Europe. However, in some instances, national contract laws or principles are cited to emphasize specific points.

- **Creation:** a contract is created if: (a) the parties intend to be legally bound, and (b) they reach a sufficient agreement. A common model for the conclusion of a contract usually follows that an offer is made by one party, which is accepted by the other party or parties. Thus, all parties involved in a contract must express their agreement to the contract. Note that it is not in all cases and/or in all jurisdictions that certain formalities such as writing, or notarization are required to conclude a valid contract.
- **Content of the contract:** Contracts have elements that are mandatory with respect to their content. This requirement is related to the “certainty” of the contract, which implies clearly defining the contractual obligations of all parties and other elements such as the specification of the parties, the price, etc. For example, in a data sharing contract, the parties involved must be defined, as well as the subject matter of the sharing (the concerned data) and the conditions of the sharing, e.g., the price, the duration, among others. Where personal data is involved, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC) further requires the parties to define the data protection actors – the data controller and data processor, and their responsibilities.

2.2. Digital contract

A digital contract is a contract, which is “entered into by two or more parties over an electronic communication line” (Weber, R. H., Contractual Duties and Allocation of Liability in Automated Digital Contracts, in: Schulze/Staudenmayer (eds.), Digital Revolution: Challenges for Contract Law in Practice, 2016, p. 163 (165 with further references)). Where such a contract is considered as information society services, Article 10 of the e-Commerce Directive (Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce, in the Internal Market) requires certain information to be provided to the recipient of the service, including:

- The technical steps to follow to conclude the contract;
- Whether the contract will be filed and accessible;
- The technical means which are used to identify and correct preceding input errors;
- The languages offered for the conclusion of the contract; and
- Indication of relevant codes of conduct, including information on how to access these codes of conduct electronically.

In addition, the contract terms and conditions must be made available in a way that allows for storage and reproduction. If digital means replace contract documents in physical form, this has a further implication for the creation and management of the contract. For example, a traditional contract in writing is stored in a secure place for preservation and it is signed twice by both parties so that each party receives the same document. Such procedures aim at securing documentation of the contract and preventing subsequent alteration by one party. This should be replicated in a digital contract. Some commentators suggest storing the digital contract “on various redundant hard drives or media devices which enable retrievals” (Weber, R. H., Contractual Duties and Allocation of Liability in Automated Digital Contracts, in: Schulze/Staudenmayer (eds.), Digital Revolution: Challenges for Contract Law in Practice, 2016, p. 163 (181)).

2.3. Smart contract

A smart contract represents an automated way of executing an agreement. The UK’s Law Commission (UK Law Commission, Smart legal contracts Advice to Government, November 2021, vii) defines a smart contract as “computer code that, upon the occurrence of a specified condition or conditions, is capable of running automatically according to pre-specified functions”. It is because of the self-executing nature of a smart contract that it is also referred to as an “automated contract”.

There are several classifications of a smart contract. For example, Schrepel (Schrepel, T., Smart Contracts and the Digital Single Market Through the Lens of a “Law + Technology” Approach, European Commission, October 2021, p. 24-25) classifies it into three, namely: i) a smart contract combined with a “legal contract”, i.e., a contract recognized by the law; ii) a smart contract without the support of a legal contract. iii) smart contracts combined with other smart contracts to create the conditions for the decentralized governance of (autonomous) ecosystems.

For a smart contract to be legally binding, all the elements required by law must be present in its creation and execution. Some legal reforms in the EU are addressing some issues relating to smart contracts, indicating some requirements to make such contracts secure. For example, Article 30 of the proposed Data Act (Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data, COM(2022) 68 final) contains some essential requirements regarding smart contracts for data sharing:

- (a) robustness: ensure that the smart contract has been designed to offer a very high degree of robustness to avoid functional errors and to withstand manipulation by third parties;

- (b) safe termination and interruption: ensure that a mechanism exists to terminate the continued execution of transactions: the smart contract shall include internal functions which can reset or instruct the contract to stop or interrupt the operation to avoid future (accidental) executions;
- (c) data archiving and continuity: foresee, if a smart contract must be terminated or deactivated, a possibility to archive transactional data, the smart contract logic and code to keep the record of the operations performed on the data in the past (auditability); and
- (d) access control: a smart contract shall be protected through rigorous access control mechanisms at the governance and smart contract layers.

Furthermore, the vendor of a smart contract and other relevant actors shall perform a conformity assessment to comply with the essential legal requirements and issue an EU declaration of conformity thereafter. Adherence to EU harmonised standards in this area is also required, where such exist.

In summary, entities engaging in digital or smart contracts within the smashHit infrastructure must comply with the legal requirements relating to the formation of the contract, the content of the contract (its terms), security requirements, where applicable, rules relating to information society services, and any other requirements applicable within the relevant jurisdiction of the contract.

3. Privacy/Security Issues

Privacy, data protection and cybersecurity are important requirements that any actor in the information society must take seriously. In the EU, several rules have been made requiring data controllers, processors, manufacturers, and service providers to implement certain measures to protect not only the personal data they process, but also implement appropriate technical and organisational measures (TOMs) to secure their information systems. The GDPR, for example, includes several principles and obligations that data controllers and processor must comply with, which in a nutshell include:

- Observing the principles of data protection (Art. 5 GDPR)
- Complying with the various obligations applicable to the specific data processing operation, including record keeping, the appointment of a data protection officer, conducting a data protection impact assessment, adopting the data protection by design approach, and providing necessary information to the data subjects, among others.
- Facilitating the enforcement of the data subjects' rights
- Implementing appropriate data security measures, among others.

One transparency requirement is that data controllers and processors must have a policy that is publicly available to others who interact with them. The law also provides the content of certain information to be provided to the data subjects. Below, the privacy policy of smashHit is shown to inform those who interact with the platform, of the various measures adopted by the platform to comply with these legal requirements.

3.1. smashHit Privacy Policy

3.1.1. Preamble

smashHit provides an infrastructure comprising different modules including a consent management tool, a dispatcher, a contract support tool, a traceability module and security and privacy (S&P) mechanisms. These tools can process personal data for specified purposes.

The smashHit platform is designed according to the principles of privacy by design and by default in the meaning of Art. 25 GDPR to ensure that all processing of personal data within smashHit will comply with the applicable rules for the processing of personal data set by the GDPR.

This privacy policy provides relevant information to users of the smashHit system, particularly on how the system implements appropriate technical and organisational measures (TOMs) to ensure and be able to demonstrate that personal data processing is performed in accordance with the GDPR.

The policy contains information relating to the role of smashHit as a data processor.

3.1.2. smashHit as a data processor and its responsibilities

smashHit processes personal data on behalf of the data controller users of the smashHit system. These data controllers determine the purposes and means of the processing. smashHit acts as a data processor for the processing of personal data within the smashHit system.

Therefore, smashHit will implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and be able to demonstrate that all processing of personal data by smashHit is performed in accordance with the applicable data protection laws. Those measures will be highlighted below.

3.1.3. Personal data processed by smashHit

smashHit collects and processes the following data directly from the **data controllers** that use our system:

- email address of the data controller
- email address of the data subject who is in contractual relationship with the data controller.

We also collect the following data indirectly from the data controllers that use our system through a web browser:

- IP address
- Technical details from the devices used to access our system.

We also collect the following data indirectly when a data subject uses our system through a web browser:

- IP address
- Technical details from the devices used to access our system.

3.1.4. Purpose of data processing

smashHit uses the personal data provided to it under the applicable data processing terms with a data controller to confirm the information received by the controller on the processing and on the consent declaration by the data subject. This process is known as 'consent certification'. Subsequently, data is processed to provide data subjects with the ability to manage their consent.

3.1.5. Legal basis for data processing

The legal basis for the processing of personal data within the smashHit environment (where smashHit is a processor) is dependent on the relationship between the data controller and the data subject. For example, such legal basis could be a consent given by the data subject (Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR), or where the processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party (Art. 6(1)(b) GDPR), or where the processing is necessary for the purposes of legitimate interests pursued by the controller subject to overriding interests of the data subject (Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR).

However, the relationship between smashHit and the controller is defined by the contract between these two actors (in accordance with Art. 28(3) GDPR).

3.1.6. Consent Management within the smashHit platform

smashHit provides a platform tool to simplify the process of consent for consumers to access data-based services. smashHit provides the necessary tools to display relevant information to the data subject concerning the consent he or she had granted, and to enable them to withdraw their consent should they wish to do so any time electronically via the consent management function and user interface. In case of consent withdrawal, smashHit will immediately inform all relevant parties that have been permitted to process the personal data by the consent.

smashHit does not store the document used to obtain consent. Such documents are kept by the data controller. smashHit however notifies the data controller when consent is withdrawn through the smashHit system.

3.1.7. Automated decision-making

smashHit does not process personal data for automatic decision-making that will produce legal effects on data subjects or similarly significantly affect the data subjects.

3.1.8. Duties of smashHit as a data processor

As a data processor, the GDPR imposes the following duties on smashHit:

- Record keeping

- processing only on the instructions of the data controller
- security measures, TOMs
- data breach notification
- at the choice of the controller, deletion or return of all the personal data to the controller after the end of the provision of services relating to processing, and deletion of existing copies unless Union or Member State law requires storage of the personal data
- making available to the controller all information necessary to demonstrate compliance with smashHit's obligations and allow for and contribute to audits, including inspections, conducted by the controller or another auditor mandated by the controller.

3.1.9. Data Subjects Rights

A data subject has several rights under the GDPR, such as:

- The right of access (Art. 15 GDPR): data subjects have the right to request from smashHit copies of the subject's personal data.
- The right to rectification (Art. 16 GDPR): data subjects have the right to request that smashHit corrects any information the data subject believes is inaccurate.
- The right to erasure (Art. 17 GDPR): data subjects have the right to request that smashHit erases subject's personal data, under certain conditions.
- The right to restrict processing (Art. 18 GDPR)
- The right to data portability (Art. 20 GDPR)
- The right to object to processing (Art. 21 GDPR)
- The right to avoid automated decision-making (Art. 22 GDPR).

Data subjects can exercise any of these rights by contacting: info@smashhit.eu

3.1.10. Cookies and how smashHit uses them

Cookies are text files placed on visitor's computer to collect standard Internet log information and visitor's behavioural information. When someone uses the smashHit web application, we may collect information from the visitor automatically through cookies or similar technology as follows: We use our own instance of the FIWARE identity manager "Keyrock"¹ to handle the authentication and authorisation of users. This instance of Keyrock makes use of three cookies: two cookies are used to keep the session (session & session.sig cookies), and a third cookie is a CSRF cookie (_csrf cookie). The CSRF cookie is used as a security measure to protect smashHit from cross-site request forgery attacks when using the session cookies. Apart from these, we do not use any other cookies.

3.1.11. Security of personal data

As specified in the data processing terms with the applicable data controller, smashHit takes reasonable and appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect personal data from loss, misuse, and inappropriate access. We use standard, industry-wide practices such as firewalls, encryption of data at rest and in transit, and (in certain areas) Secure Socket Layers ("SSL") to protect users' information.

3.1.12. Data retention and storage

Storage periods depend on the data processing terms with our data controller user and the individual data subjects. smashHit securely stores personal data as long as the terms of processing with the data controller permit.

3.1.13. Children

smashHit does not direct its data processing service to children.

¹ For information see <https://fiware-idm.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

3.1.14. Sharing with third parties

smashHit does not share personal data with third parties.

3.1.15. Transfer of personal data to third countries

smashHit does not transfer personal data to third countries.

3.1.16. Changes to our privacy policy

smashHit keeps its privacy policy under regular review and places any updates on its web page. This privacy policy was last updated in September 2022.

3.1.17. How to contact us

Any questions about smashHit's privacy policy, the data smashHit is processing about you as a data subject, or if you as a data subject would like to exercise any of your data protection rights, please do not hesitate to contact: info@smashhit.eu

3.2. Important Note for Data Controllers

3.2.1. Data controllers and their responsibilities

Users of the smashHit system as data controllers must ensure that all processing of personal data via their infrastructure has a legal basis. It is the responsibility of such data controller to identify the legal basis for processing. As data controllers, you are responsible for disclosing the rights of individuals and other information regarding the collection and use of their personal data, in accordance with the GDPR.

3.2.2. Information to be provided to the data subjects

Upon collection of personal data from data subjects, data controllers must ensure that they provide all the necessary information to the data subjects according to the GDPR.

3.2.3. Obtaining consent from the data subjects

As data controllers, you must obtain consent from the data subject and such consent must be given by a clear affirmative act establishing a freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's agreement to the processing of personal data relating to her or him (Art. 6 (1), Recital 32 of the GDPR). Data subjects must be properly informed about the purposes of the processing of their personal data in clear and plain language. Data subjects must be informed that consent can be withdrawn at any time by the data subject without any negative consequences for the data subject.

3.2.4. Establish a contractual relationship with smashHit as a data processor

Data controllers that engage the services of a data processor must establish a contractual relationship according to Article 28(3) of the GDPR.

In summary, entities acting as data controllers within the smashHit infrastructure must comply with the legal requirements imposed by the GDPR and other applicable regulations with respect to the collection, processing, storage, deletion or archiving of personal data, throughout the data lifecycle.

F.A.Q.

smashHit platform

Q: What is the smashHit platform?

A: smashHit is a platform that provides a generic, transparent way to view and manage consent certificates supported by disrupting technologies such as traceability of use of data, data fingerprinting and automatic contracting among the data owners, data provider, and service providers.

Q: How can I join smashHit?

A: In order to make sure the process is as straight-forward as possible for data owners, your registration in smashHit will be automatically handled by us when you sign your first consent with any of the approved smashHit partners.

Instructions to access smashHit will be sent to the email address you've indicated to the organization requesting consent.

Legal framework for contracts

Q: What do I need to comply with when engaging into a digital, smart or automated contract via smashHit?

A: Digital and automated contracts have several legal implications and raise several questions related to, e.g., the formation of such a contract, its content, and the security requirements to be complied with, see section 2 of this document.

Requirements of digital and automated contracts

Q: What are the key elements, and requirements of entering a legally binding contractual relationship via electronic means or with automated elements?

A: There are certain legal requirements related to the creation and the content of a contract as well as specific requirements depending on the concrete type and nature of the contract, see section 2.1 of this document.

Digital contract

Q: Are there any specific legal requirements for a digital contract and if yes, which?

A: Yes, there are specific legal requirements for digital contracts, see section 2.2 of this document.

Smart contract

Q: Are there any specific legal requirements for a digital contract and if yes, which?

A: Yes, there are specific legal requirements for digital contracts, they are described in section 2.3 of this document.

Relevance of privacy, data protection and cybersecurity

Q: What is the role of privacy, data protection and cybersecurity in the context of the smashHit system?

A: Privacy, data protection and cybersecurity play an important role as several instruments like the General Data Protection Regulation set rules for any actor in the information society, see section 3 of this document.

Role of smashHit with regard to privacy and data protection

Q: What is the role of smashHit in terms of privacy, data protection and security?

A: smashHit acts as a data processor, see section 3.1.2 of this document.

Information on details of processing and on the protection of privacy

Q: Where do I find information regarding the processing of personal data by smashHit, e.g. which data is processed by smashHit, how, for what purpose, and on which basis?

A: You will find such information in particular in the smashHit privacy policy in section 3.1 of this document.

Rights of natural persons

Q: What rights do I have as a natural person whose data is being processed by smashHit and how can I enforce them?

A: As a data subject you have a number of rights - see section 3.1.9 of this document, where you will also find information on what they imply, as well as contact details should you wish to exercise them. You will find information on how to contact us also in section 3.1.17 of this document.

Data controllers

Q: I am using smashHit as a data controller. Is there anything I have to observe?

A: Yes, it is important to know that as a data controller you have your own responsibilities, please see the respective note for data controllers in section 3.2 of this document.

Glossary

Automated contract: Contract or agreement which is executed automatically, see also → smart contract

Data controller: Legal term from the → GDPR - a body (e.g. a public authority or a company), which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data

Data processor: Legal term from the → GDPR - a body which processes personal data on behalf of a → data controller

Data subject: Legal term in the → GDPR used in a context where personal data is processed determining the person to whom an information is or can be related. The data subject is a natural person who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by a factor specific to her or his physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.

Digital contract: A contract concluded via electronic means

E-Commerce Directive: A legal norm on EU level to be transformed into national law by the EU Member States, laying down rules for electronic commerce related to information society services, e.g. the internet

GDPR: Abbreviation for 'General Data Protection Regulation', a legal norm on EU level adopted in 2016, which is directly applicable within its scope and lays down rules for the processing of personal data so as to protect natural persons' fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data

Personal data: Legal term in the → GDPR - any information related to an identified or identifiable natural person (see → data subject), e.g. a name or a home address

Smart contract: Automatic way of executing an agreement, in particular a contract, see also → automated contract

TOM(s): Technical and organisational measure/measures taken to ensure that processing of personal data is carried out in accordance with the rules of the → GDPR and to safeguard the rights and freedoms of → data subjects; the measures can be related to the security of the processing, e.g. the pseudonymisation or encryption of personal data

➤ **Our vision** - Solving Consumer Consent & Data Security for Connected Car and Smart City

➤ **Further information**

This document is part of the smashHit Methodology. The complete set of documents, including other user/developer guides as well as white papers created within this scope can be found on our website:

<https://smashhit.eu/publications>

➤ **Our consortium**

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